

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

PEER AUDITS OF ELECTRONIC MEDICAL RECORDS:
STRATEGY FOR QUALITY PERFORMANCE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Cheryl D. Pearce

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Dana N. Rutledge, PhD, RN, Project Chair
Suzanne Robertson, PhD, RN, Committee Member

May 2015

Copyright Cheryl Diane Pearce 2015 ©

ABSTRACT

This project involved developing a medical record audit process within a shared learning environment, and evaluation of nurse learning and perceptions that enhance/hinder audit participation. Two tools were developed: an audit tool with metrics to determine changes in documentation quality, and a survey assessing learning/audit process perceptions. Fifteen Certified Nurse Midwives (CNMs) participated in the audit process, and completed perception surveys pre- and post-audit. Surveys assessed factors that potentially enhance or hinder the audit process in three domains: Learning, Reluctance, and Time. CNMs audited 3-5 randomly selected electronic medical records (EMRs) from another CNM to assess adequacy and placement for items related to prenatal care. After audits were complete, CNMs reviewed aggregate audit quality scores and discussed learnings from the audit experiences and methods to improve documentation. There was a significant decrease in perceptions of reluctance in audit participation ($p < .001$). Additionally, review of individual item scores showed that CNMs perceived that they had learned from the experience, valued the audit process in terms of potentially enhancing documentation of care, and felt the time spent for audits was worthwhile.. Results highlighted the need for adequate time to conduct audits. This study suggests that an audit process with a shared learning team approach may yield benefits of changes in perceptions about documentation quality.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vi
LIST OF FIGURES.....	vii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	viii
BACKGROUND.....	1
Problem Statement.....	1
Purpose Statement.....	6
Peer Audit Learning (PAL) Supporting Framework.....	10
Shared Learning Theory.....	11
Conscious Competence Learning Model.....	11
Peer Audit Learning (PAL) Framework.....	12
REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....	14
Overview.....	14
Standards for Prenatal Care.....	14
Why Prenatal Care for the First Audits?.....	14
Fetal Outcomes.....	15
Maternal Outcomes.....	15
Birth Outcomes in the United States.....	16
Prenatal Care Content.....	17
Prenatal Care Content in the United States.....	19
CNM Prenatal Care in Orange County, CA.....	20
Conclusion.....	22
Documentation Audits.....	25
Benefits Associated with Audits.....	25
Costs Associated with Audits.....	26
Conclusion.....	27
Error Discovery.....	28
Potential Types of Error.....	28
Participation in Audits and Error Discovery.....	29
Ethics of Error Reporting.....	29
Error disclosure: The patient.....	29
Error disclosure: The provider.....	30
Current NHCS Error Reporting Policies.....	31

Conclusion	33
Review of Literature Conclusion	33
METHODS	35
Ethical Considerations	35
Documentation Audit Error Discovery	35
Participation in Documentation Audit Study	36
Participants	36
Instruments	36
Audit Tool: Peer Audit Tool (PAT)	36
Survey: Peer Audit Learning Team (PALT) Survey	39
Procedures	41
Audit Process: Use of the PAT	41
Preparation	41
Audits	41
Post-audit Debriefings	42
Future Audits	42
Survey Process: PALT Survey	43
Data Analysis	43
Audits: PAT	43
Surveys: PALT Surveys	44
RESULTS	45
Peer Documentation Audits: PAT	45
Surveys: PALT Surveys	46
Demographics	46
PALT Surveys: Learning, Reluctance and Time	46
DISCUSSION	55
Results Related to Learning	56
Results Related to Reluctance	56
Results Related to Time	57
Limitations	57
Conclusions	57
Plan for Implementation and Dissemination of Findings	59
REFERENCES	61
APPENDIX A: PERMISSION FOR USE OF “PYRAMID FOR CARE” BY K. NICOLAIDES, MD	66
APPENDIX B: PEER AUDIT LEARNING TEAM (PALT) SURVEY	67

APPENDIX C: AUTHOR GUIDELINES FOR NWH.....	71
APPENDIX D: TABLES OF EVIDENCE	75
Audits	75
Shared Learning	83
Participation and Error Discovery	85
Prenatal Care Guidelines and Evidence	86

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Peer Audit Tool (PAT) Scoring System	38
2. Documentation Quality Index (DQI) Computation	39
3. Initial Prenatal Care Visit Documentation Audit Results	46
4. Demographics of Survey Participants.....	48
5. Learning Perception Survey Results.....	49
6. Reluctance Perception Table Results.....	50
7. Time Perception Survey Results.....	51
8. Perceived Time and Actual Time Needed for Each Audit	52

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Theoretical framework for documentation audits.....	10
2. Nicolaides Prenatal Care Pyramids.....	20
3. Peer Audit Tool (PAT) Side A for initial prenatal care visit documentation	23
3. Peer Audit Tool (PAT) Side B for initial prenatal care visit documentation	24
4. Comparison of results categorized by the three domains	53
5. Perceived time to complete audit compared to actual time	53

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank my Midwifery colleagues, not only in their support of this research but in their support as peers, Midwives, friends and sisters. Without their dedication to women, this study, as well as our practice would not be possible.

Additionally I would like to thank Kaiser Permanente for allowing this research, and especially Patrick N. Roth, MD, and Denise E. Dunne, RN, as well as the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology in Orange County, California.

I would like to thank my family, for tolerating all that is required when a family member is in school: missed dinners, books and papers in the bedroom, dining room and office, pinch hitting for social functions, and offering hot coffee on those long nights.

Lastly, I thank my soul mate, Mike, who knows what goes unsaid . . . with a prayer, our marriage will last another 39 years.

BACKGROUND

Accurate documentation is a mainstay of providing quality health care and monitoring its quality. Communication among members of the entire health care team depends upon documented assessments and care delivered; the absence of such documentation can affect the quality of care provided. Recent technological advances in electronic medical records (EMR) have made EMR use integral to many health care agencies. Correctly used, EMR provides clear documentation of patient health care histories, and is available instantaneously to all team members wherever they may be physically located. In my obstetrical practice, our team includes physicians, Certified Nurse Midwives (CNMs), nurses, support staff, radiologists, and laboratory technicians. Prenatal care is comprised of multiple office visits assessing maternal and fetal status. Findings from a range of standard laboratory and ultrasound tests are documented, along with more detailed testing if indicated. The documentation must provide efficient incorporation and integration of all data generated so that all team members can provide effective and appropriate care. Accurate and reliable information about factors such as gestational age is imperative to care decisions in the perinatal arena (Kamath et al., 2012).

Problem Statement

As EMR technology emerges, strategies for teaching the use of EMR are also developing. CNMs employed by a large national health care system (NHCS) use an EMR system. This comprehensive EMR is one of the largest private electronic health systems in the world. Now used in 37 hospitals and 611 medical offices, EMR use began locally in 2007. EMR has completely replaced all paper charts (Kaiser Permanente, 2014a). EMR is a computerized data and order entry system that provides team members with access to all

aspects of the medical record including provider entered notes, laboratory, radiology and pathology reports, and treatment plans. Outside records are scanned into the system, becoming available when providers check the specific section for “outside records.”

All NCHS providers, nurses, and ancillary staff receive training on the use of this system, and receive further training as technological developments require updates to EMRs. Despite universal training, use varies from area to area, and from individual to individual. Furthermore, the comprehensive nature of the EMRS leads to different tabs, fields, and pages where the same information can be entered. Currently, data entered into one tab or field may not automatically populate into corresponding tabs or fields creating the need for redundant data entry.

While designed as a comprehensive medical record, over time, users have reported that the EMR lacks many aspects specific to perinatal care. Thus, improvements are constantly developing as different phases of the technology are implemented or “go live.” This necessitates frequent updates and training. Ghartey et al. (2014) evaluated the adequacy of prenatal records in Bronx, New York comparing standardized paper prenatal records with EMR prenatal records and found that adequacy of documentation is related to the type of practice, rather than the type of record.

As staff members receive training on the new aspects of the EMR, currently, there is no ongoing assessment of documentation skills and chart completeness. Standardizing completeness and location of health information would streamline care delivery. For example, the labor unit admits a near term, bleeding pregnant woman. Diagnosed with placenta previa during her prenatal care, she now needs immediate evaluation by the provider who is typically meeting her for the first time, and is relying on her records for

critical information. Upon opening her record, providers note the problem list on the first page. This list highlights important facts crucial to her care. Making an accurate diagnosis of the cause of the bleeding is quicker and more likely when the problem list features “placenta previa.” Unfortunately, the EMR currently allows for listing the placenta previa in a variety of places, many of which would not lead to this condition becoming a listed problem. Many such entries do not automatically migrate into the problem list. This may lead to delay in recognizing crucial data.

As the EMR matures and becomes more complex, outdated information can remain in locations such as the problem list, or the medication list. This can mislead providers. Cleaning up, or archiving outdated information is not fully automated in EMR, and requires time and energy from providers. This cleanup process is frequently overlooked. When admitting patients to the hospital, providers are faced with the task of editing the problem list, medication list, and the history sections.

Another concept that further leads to inefficient use of the EMR is what we refer to as “mud hutting.” This occurs when information is entered without regard to what is already there and leads to redundancies that make it difficult to locate key items, especially when an item is only entered into a progress note. The progress notes are listed by date, but can be sorted by provider type, department type, inpatient or outpatient, or procedure notes. However, providers need to be aware that the note exists and where it is located. If it was not added to the problem list, providers may not be aware of the need to search for the note, or providers may not have the computer skills to find the information.

Computers were not routinely used in education until the 1990s (Fouts, 2000). Until recently, computer and typing skills were not included in the training of nurses

(McAlearney, Sieck, Hefner, Robbins, & Huerta, 2013). Entering information on a computer screen is a very different experience than hand writing a note. There are pop-up screens, toolbars, and multiple pages that need navigation. It is not just a matter of typing a few sentences. This can be intimidating, especially for those who did not come of age in the current computer era or who have minimal computer skills (Fujino & Kawamoto, 2013). These issues can lead to poor documentation. Parsons, McCullough, Wang, and Shih (2012) recommended close scrutiny of the EMR prior to using it as a source for assessment of provider performance or payment. They found that while providers are trained on proper documentation techniques during initial training, there are no mechanisms to cause providers to document in specific locations within the EMR. Many providers had reverted to same patterns that they had used in paper documentation once they discovered that they could simply write a stand-alone progress note. If information is only within the note, the EMR functionality is decreased. Frequently, when the EMR is assessed for compliance or reimbursement, only the form field coding areas are utilized. Since these audits do not search within the typed note that does not utilize links within the EMR system, this information is not recognized. When comparing the features of EMR records system to the actual typed documents, true provider performance for compliance of components for care is underestimated.

At the same time, Parsons et al. (2012) found an overestimation of the skill levels for providers in using the EMR system. Without continued feedback on documentation skills, providers may not even be aware of deficits in their entries. Based on their findings, they recommended standardization of the various medical record components in order to improve the quality and completeness of those records.

Currently, EMR documentation review in my practice is only performed as a response to a request for a review, from a Risk Management request, a patient or provider complaint, or other specific trigger conditions. Examples of triggers are the diagnosis of ruptured ectopic pregnancy in a woman who had already established prenatal care, undiagnosed placenta previa, or low newborn Apgar scores assessed at time of delivery. As we currently only review records when referred after a problem, clinicians who have expected outcomes (and no problems or triggers) do not have their documentation reviewed. If an outcome is unexpected but the review demonstrates that the care was appropriate, the provider is not notified of the review, or of the review results. Providers are only notified when their actions, either physical or in the documentation, are found to be directly contributory to the patient's outcome. As a result, CNMs may not be aware of adequacy or inadequacy of their EMR documentation.

As a member of the Peer Review committee at my facility, I review the EMR charts generated by CNMs and have found wide variances in documentation. It is apparent that there is a need to standardize prenatal records, and develop a mechanism that provides for individual nurse feedback and updating of records. While all CNMs are competent entering basic notes, their completeness varies widely.

Based on peer reviews, it is apparent that many providers demonstrate a lack of ability to navigate through the various EMR modules. Some do not use EMR features that auto populate other fields, making it difficult to locate important data. For instance, a provider can write the complete history and physical as a stand-alone progress note, without using any of the "drop down" fields. While from a legal standpoint this is considered an adequate note, it does little to assist team members. In this case, they would

need to search through the progress notes to locate the data; and if unaware of the note's existence, it is very likely they would not perform this search. Unfortunately, the second provider is expected to consider the history in providing care, even if it is deep inside the body of the EMR, because it is still available for review.

All of the above informed the choice to develop a prototype strategy of record review in a shared learning environment, and to develop standards for what constitutes adequate documentation throughout prenatal care. This will include metrics to determine whether documentation has improved. At the NHCS, documentation and review standards need to be developed for several key diagnosis conditions in women's health: (a) antenatal care in the office setting; (b) intrapartum care; and (c), gynecological care in the office setting. For this project, only antenatal care in the office setting is addressed. Once developed, this strategy for quality improvement (QI) of the EMR can be applied to other areas of women's health care. The expectation is that improved documentation and EMR usage will lead to better, efficient care from the CNM team.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this QI project is to improve documentation within the NCHS EMR during obstetrical and gynecological care by members of the CNM service. The goal is to standardize documentation elements as well as documentation location within the EMR of specific elements identified as standard requirements for the initial prenatal office visit. To accomplish this goal, I developed an audit tool for low risk prenatal care based upon evidence-based practice standards. It was used by participating CNMs to perform systematic chart audits. These audits promoted peer assessment for accuracy and adequacy of documentation. Through regular reviews of EMRs, CNM auditors became familiar

with comparing the audit standard and documentation standards. This prompted collegial discussion of documentation in the EMR and identified areas considered adequate or inadequate. The CNM team then strategized how to address problem areas, and develop more uniform practices in documentation.

A second main purpose for this project is to establish a formalized setting for addressing problems while promoting shared learning. We will need to demonstrate benefit to the NCHS for this activity. If we are to take work time to perform EMR audits, and discuss the audits in-team meetings, then data must be provided to NCHS to demonstrate the impact of these activities on documentation quality (an index of patient care).

To accomplish establishing a forum for chart audits, while providing evidence to the NCHS that there is value in investment for this project, several project activities occurred which addressed the following questions:

1. “What are the standards for antenatal care?” In order to assess whether the documentation was adequate, we must assess whether care is adequate based on minimal standards as set forth by our medical group as well as by professional organizations in antenatal care. These include, but are not limited to, standards established by the World Health Organization (WHO), National Institutes of Health (NIH), Centers for Disease Control (CDC), and the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG).
2. “What rubric or audit tool will be used to assess the documentation?” Once baseline antenatal care standards were established, a tool was developed and

used to perform the chart audits. This tool will be based on the standards as established in Question 1.

3. “What is the baseline quality or adequacy of documentation, and how does participation in the audits affect documentation?” By participation in the audits by the NCHS CNM service, will we see a positive effect, or improvement in the quality of documentation as demonstrated over time? This question is to be addressed post-doctoral project.
4. “How do CNMs perceive chart audits, and do they perceive benefit by participation?” In order to assess whether CNMs believe that this was a worthy endeavor, they were surveyed at baseline and post-audit process about several aspects of their participation. The survey developed included concepts of:
 - a. *Reluctance*. Was there a fear, or reluctance associated with audit participation? If so, was it based upon fear of punitive response, either of the audits of their own documentation, or of revealing and confronting the problems in peers’ documentation?
 - b. *Learning*. Did performing the audits permit CNMs the opportunity to learn by reviewing peer documentation? Did learning occur through the audits or did learning occur with the discussion of the audits?
 - c. *Time*. Was the time involved with the audits and discussion beneficial? Did the CNMs believe that five charts were too many, not enough? Was there value associated with the chart audits? Did they enjoy the process? Other thoughts about the process?

5. Develop a strategy for ongoing audits. As this first audit focuses on antenatal care, it will serve as a prototype for establishing teams to develop future audit tools applicable to women's health care. These include, but are not limited to intrapartum care, contraceptive care, and well women care.
6. Provide the NHCS with reports on the impact of audits of the EMR on quality outcomes. By formalizing where the CNM service uniformly documents certain aspects of the antenatal care, we should see consistent complete records in subsequent audits over the first year. This translates to improved quality patient care, and efficiency for care providers.

The NCHS system for obstetrics requires that we participate as a team. CNMs rely upon the EMR documentation to guide our care. We provide care for women when they are most vulnerable, in the process of labor and giving birth. The NCHS however, schedules CNM hospital schedules months in advance; as a result, over 90% of the time, we meet patients for the first time in the labor setting. A complete, accurate EMR should enhance provider knowledge for patients, including their specific goals for care.

Supporting Framework: Peer Audit Learning

Combined, two learning frameworks support this QI project. These include Shared Learning Theory and the Conscious Competence Learning Model (CCLM). Forming the Peer Audit Learning (PAL) framework, they each provide concepts that enhanced the potential success of this project (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Peer Audit Learning Framework. Quality improvement process in light of levels of documentation competency and learner awareness of competence. Incorporates components of Shared Learning Theory by M. Keith and N. Frese (2008) and "Conscious competence theory," by A. Chapman, March 1, 2014. Retrieved from <http://www.businessballs.com/consciouscompetencelearningmodel.htm>.

Shared Learning Theory

Theories of learning from errors and of shared learning environments strongly suggest the essential role of staff involvement in improving quality of care. Staff participation in chart audits has demonstrated the impact of such experiences on significant behavior change such as compliance with guidelines (Chang & Mark, 2011; Milchak, Shanahan, & Kerzee, 2012). Rather than focusing on reviews after an occurrence (often negative or punitive), ongoing routine reviews can create a positive learning environment among those involved.

Error management researchers have found that learning and behavior change occur when errors are shared within a culture of shared learning and changed norms (Kachalia & Bates, 2014; Keith & Frese, 2005; Sammer, Lykens, Singh, Mains, & Lackan, 2010). Shared error information and subsequent learning contributes to positive learning climates, thus, benefitting entire teams. Additionally, a positive learning climate should reduce errors as detailed information surrounding actual and near errors is shared among nursing staff, allowing behavior adjustment which prevent or minimize future problems (Chang & Mark, 2011).

Conscious Competence Learning Model (CCLM)

The concepts presented by the CCLM inform this project (see Figure 1). Attributed to many sources, the CCLM is based on the premise that learning occurs in stages, and can occur only when learners are aware of their deficiencies or lack of skill (Chapman, 2014). The four levels of learning competence are based on awareness and level of concentration needed for skill mastery: Unconsciously Incompetent, Consciously Incompetent, Consciously Competent, and Unconsciously Competent.

Initially, persons are naïve or unaware of their incompetence in a particular skill, hence the “unconscious incompetence.” It is not until discovering an incompetence that they can desire to master the skill. With mastery, they become unconsciously competent, but run the danger of regressing to a state of unconscious incompetency; hence the need for constant reassessment of the level of competency. This leads to an environment of continuous improvement.

Chapman (2014) further describes the learning process as one filled with “aha” moments, as “progression from stage to stage is often accompanied by a feeling of awakening as things 'click' into place for the learner” (para. 4). These are associated with a sense of mastery, accomplishment, and personal growth. Without this progression through the stages, learners may have self-doubts, or may find it takes great concentration or effort to produce acceptable results.

Peer Audit Learning (PAL) Framework

Based on combining the two models of CCLM and Shared Learning Theory, the Peer Audit Learning (PAL) framework was developed. In our system, CNMs vary widely in terms of level of awareness of documentation proficiency. CNMs with lack of awareness of their inadequate documentation within the EMR reflect a state of “unconscious incompetence.” Some are very much aware of their incompetence and struggle to become competent, and others have to work diligently to navigate the EMR. Through the shared learning process envisioned in this project, information gained from reviewing others’ charts can help those whose documentation is inadequate become aware of their own inadequacies. This may help to move them towards conscious competence and perhaps, to unconscious competency. The rewards would be improved documentation

and collegial sharing of tips leading to efficient documentation as described in the PAL framework.

.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

This multi-pronged QI project has several aspects that informed the basis for the literature search and review. The topics reviewed were standards for prenatal care, documentation audits, and error discovery and management. The literature was also reviewed for possible audit tool components, as well as components for the CNM audit participation survey. Databases used were PubMed, CINAHL, EBSCO, and Google Scholar. Searches were restricted to sources involving human subjects and available in English. The searches for prenatal care standards were not limited by date; however, if older than 10 years only seminal articles were used. All other searches were restricted to sources published within the last 10 years. Search result abstracts were reviewed, and if the topic was appropriate, sources were selected for further evaluation of relevance. Any sources containing evidence considered relevant were reviewed and placed into the Table of Evidence (Appendix D).

Standards for Prenatal Care

Why Prenatal Care as Topic for the First Audits?

Prenatal Care (PNC) is recognized as one of the most accessible interventions in promoting fetal development and maternal health (Chauhan, Hendrix, Berghella, & Siddiqui, 2010; Nicolaides, 2011; Vogel, Lee, & Souza, 2014; Woodhouse, Lopez Camelo, & Wehby, 2014). Worldwide, there are wide variations in PNC approaches, with equally wide variations in birth outcomes. While recognized as benefitting public health for perinatal outcomes, the recommended frequency of visits for PNC varies from four visits to over 12 in the course of a normal pregnancy when care is initiated early in the

first trimester (Dowswell et al., 2010). According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2014) one third of pregnant women in developing countries receive adequate PNC (at least four prenatal care visits), and 99% of maternal deaths occur in these countries. Countries with minimal PNC access are associated with increased infant and maternal mortality (WHO, 2012).

Fetal outcomes. Lack of PNC is associated with low birth weight (< 2500 grams), preterm birth (before 37 weeks gestation), and neonatal mortality (deaths in the first month of life) (Krans & Davis, 2012; Nicolaides, 2011; Woodhouse et al., 2014). Preterm birth occurs in approximately 15 million deliveries every year worldwide and directly contributes to the deaths of 1.1 million babies per year (Blencowe et al., 2012). More than 60% of preterm births occur in countries of low and middle incomes where PNC is significantly different from in many of the developed nations. Almost 97% of the world's preterm births occur in less developed countries (WHO, 2012). The rates of preterm births are increasing worldwide, requiring perinatal health care providers to strategize or “rethink” the efficacy of PNC (Howson, Kinney, McDougall, & Lawn, 2013).

Maternal outcomes. Women who have minimal PNC have increased risks for morbidity and mortality associated with pregnancy and childbirth. Worldwide, the leading causes for deaths are directly attributable to pregnancy factors (WHO, 2012) and in descending order include hemorrhage, infection, pre-eclampsia and eclampsia, and complicated abortion. While these account for 80% of maternal deaths worldwide, additional contributing factors include malaria and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) in pregnancy.

In developed nations, women typically receive PNC, along with having the option to give birth in clean, modern facilities, and virtually all go home healthy with new babies. According to the WHO (2012) the maternal mortality rate in developed nations averages 16 deaths per 100,000 births; while in some third world countries, the maternal mortality rate is as high as 1000 deaths per 100,000 births. Worldwide, 287,000 women died in 2010 due to complications of pregnancy. This means that a woman died every 1.83 minutes somewhere in the world from her pregnancy (WHO, 2012).

Birth outcomes in the United States. Considered a developed nation, the United States enjoys the health care outcomes afforded developed nations (Martin, Hamilton, Ventura, Osterman, & Mathews, 2013). The overall number of U.S. births in 2011 was 3,953,590, which is 1% less than the total number of births in 2010. The number of preterm births dropped by 2% (11.73% of all births, down from 11.99% in 2010) for the fifth straight year. This resulted with a drop in the low birth weight infants, despite the unchanged rate for twins and triplet births (Martin et al., 2013). This is significant because multiple births are frequently associated with preterm birth and low birth weight.

Despite advances in fetal outcomes, maternal improvements are not as apparent. The number of cesarean deliveries remains unchanged at 32.8% (Martin et al., 2013). While the maternal mortality rate worldwide in developed nations is 16 per 100,000 births (WHO, 2012), the US does not report these same outcomes. According to the Centers for Disease Control (CDC), the US maternal mortality rate has steadily increased from 7.2 deaths per 100,000 live births in 1987 to a high of 17.8 deaths per 100,000 live births in 2011 (Center for Disease Control, 2014). This may be attributable to how maternal deaths are reported. Pregnancy-related death in the United States is defined as “death of a woman

while pregnant or within 1 year of pregnancy termination—regardless of the duration or site of the pregnancy—from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management, but not from accidental or incidental causes” (Center for Disease Control 2014, “How does CDC define pregnancy-related deaths,” para. 1). Also affecting the rising maternal death rate may be the increasing average age of women who become pregnant. The mean age in the United States for first pregnancy is now 25.8 years, as compared to 21.4 years in 1970 (Martin et al., 2013). While hemorrhage and pre-eclampsia are leading causes for maternal mortality worldwide, the leading causes for maternal death in the United States were cardiovascular disease (14.6%) , infection/sepsis (14%), non-cardiovascular diseases (e.g., infectious, respiratory, gastrointestinal, endocrine, hematologic) (11.9%), and cardiomyopathy (11.8%). Hemorrhage, while the leading cause for maternal death worldwide is the fifth cause for maternal death in the United States (CDC, 2014).

When considering PNC in the United States, it becomes apparent that a key component for quality care is risk identification. As the leading cause of maternal deaths in the United States tends to be health care issues that are adversely affected by pregnancy, it is imperative that CNMs identify those women at risk so that their PNC can be tailored to address those issues. This especially concerning because, as the pregnant population becomes older, the health care risks increase (Robbins et al., 2014).

Prenatal Care Content

Women and newborns who receive little or minimal prenatal care suffer more complications of pregnancy, but is it the amount of PNC that makes a difference, or the content and quality of PNC? Alexander and Kotelchuck (2001) question the historical

measurement of “adequate” prenatal care as based on number of prenatal care visits. Most observational studies for birth outcomes use number of visits during a pregnancy as the indicator for adequate care, rather than the content of the visits (Dowswell et al., 2010). Much of the content of PNC or frequency for visits has been established with little or no evidence, and is the focus of research by experts within perinatal care (Avery, Montgomery, & Brandl-Salutz, 2012; Chauhan et al., 2010; Dowswell et al., 2010; Glantz, 2012; National Institute for Health and Care Excellence [NICE]. 2014; Nicolaides, 2011; Villar et al., 2013).

Currently under assessment is the comparative clinical and cost effectiveness of PNC strategies, as well as women’s preferences in care. Dowswell et al. (2010) point out that prior observational studies showed that women who receive antenatal care have lower maternal and perinatal mortality with better pregnancy outcomes. They further emphasized it was not the amount of PNC, but that the PNC includes “activities supported by reasonable evidence of effectiveness and safety” (p. 3).

In addition to PNC, what factors contribute to the complications that arise during pregnancy in the United States? Alexander and Kotelchuck (2001) state that women who are health conscious are more likely to initiate PNC early and attend most visits as scheduled. However, these same women are more likely to participate in health-promoting activities, maintain a balanced diet, and abstain from tobacco, alcohol, and illicit drugs. They are also more likely to plan their pregnancies and obtain health care when not pregnant (Alexander & Kotelchuck, 2001). When these factors are considered, is it the PNC, or the generally good health status that affects birth outcomes? These considerations play a role in audit tool development.

Prenatal care content in the United States. Alexander and Kotelchuck (2001) report most pregnant women in the United States have PNC as recommended by the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologist (ACOG) criteria. They point out that many traditional components of PNC efficacy have not been rigorously tested. As new changes are implemented, these have been added to existing PNC standards of care, rather than replacing outdated standards. Adherence to standards can vary, but interestingly, ACOG found that CNMs are the providers who most closely followed PNC guidelines and were also most likely to implement new evidence-based protocols (Baldwin, Raine, Jenkins, Hart, & Rosenblatt, 1994).

The current recommended schedule for PNC is 8 to 14 visits beginning in the first trimester. The initial visit is considered the most crucial, establishing gestational dating, assessing health and pregnancy risk factors, and performing initial screening processes such as laboratory tests. At this visit, a woman is categorized as having either a low-risk or high-risk pregnancy.

Nicolaides (2011) has proposed a completely different approach to prenatal care based on the results of this initial visit (Figure 2). This care model allows for shifting resources for care for those who need specialized, disease-specific care during pregnancy. Figure 2 compares that the past model of care with increasing frequency of visits for all women to one based on risk stratification.

Figure 2. Past model of Pregnancy care . . . and that of the Future. Prenatal care pyramids by K. Nicolaides (2011). A model for a new pyramid of prenatal care based on the 11 to 13 weeks assessment. *Prenatal Diagnosis*, 31, p. 3. Used with permission (Appendix A).

While Nicolaides (2011) concepts “turns us over” in our approach to PNC, Dowswell et al. (2010) cautions us to remember that women may prefer the standard visit model (8 to 12 visits) and may perceive the reduced visit schedule (5 or fewer visits) as having the gaps between care visits that are too long. The comprehensive review by Dowswell et al. (2011) demonstrated significantly increased perinatal mortality associated with reduced visits in low-income and middle-income countries. This suggests that reducing the visit schedule must be accompanied by close assessment of fetal and neonatal outcomes. Dowswell et al. (2011) also report that the number of inductions of labors and births by cesarean section were similar for women who had standard visit schedules compared to those who had reduced visit schedules.

CNM Prenatal Care in Orange County, CA. In 2012, there were 3,952,841 births in the United States (Martin et al., 2013). That same year, the 19 CNMs who comprise our CNM team delivered 2909 babies, or almost 0.1% of all the babies born in the United States that year. We delivered 3203 babies in 2014, and have steadily increased

our numbers every year for a total of just over 70,000 babies delivered by our CNM team since 1980. While the national cesarean section rate is 32.8% (Martin et al., 2013), our cesarean section rate is 11.9%. However, it is important to recognize that we care for primarily low risk women with a single gestation who should require minimal interventions, supporting Nicolaides' theory.

The PNC schedule used currently is ~12 visits when a woman's gestation lasts 41 weeks. There are two initial visits in the first trimester, and each lasts approximately 30 minutes. The first one (6-8 weeks) establishes dates, assesses health history, contains a complete history and physical performance, and reviews the screening tools for domestic violence, and depression, and review of the prenatal questionnaire. Teratogen risk reduction, dietary and exercise guidelines are reviewed and miscarriage precautions are discussed. Emergency contact information is given.

Reviewing the evidence, our care approximates recommendations suggested by National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2014) as well as those provided by WHO (Banta, 2003). Evidence suggests positive recommendations for continuing our practice. The *Standard Prenatal Schedule* utilized in our setting was revised in October 2013. It essentially matches the WHO antenatal care model basic component checklist (Banta, 2003, p. 17) with the addition of the fetal survey ultrasound performed at 18 to 20 weeks of gestational age. Banta (2003) indicated that Midwifery care results in equal outcomes of care with the added benefit of lower frequency of interventions. It is associated with lower costs, and increased maternal satisfaction. Banta's findings support Midwifery care as effective with the specific advantages attributable to that care. Banta (2003) also cautioned that while low risk women may not need services generally

identified as appropriate for high-risk pregnancies, medico-legal implications make it difficult to reduce services not clearly indicated by the low risk stratification. He reported that courts in the United States, Canada, and the United Kingdom have found physicians guilty of not providing high-risk care, contributing to physicians providing care that is otherwise thought to be unnecessary.

Conclusion

It appears that the current standards of PNC as practiced within our service appear to be effective and meet the ACOG, WHO, CDC, and NICE standards. An audit tool was developed for the documentation of that care within the prenatal record (Figures 3 & 4). With these audits, we can standardize not only what we document, but also where we document.

Documentation Audit Tool: First Prenatal Visit (SIDE A)									
Auditor: _____									
1st Audits	Document # _____		Lat 3 Digits of Chart Number	_____	_____	_____	_____	Reviewer	to Complete
Entered Care at Approx GA (weeks)	_____						Raw Totals	Applicable (# of Yes)	
	Score	Description		Score	Description		Score	Description	
Past Medical History .pmh	-1	Applicable but not present	Allergies	-1	Applicable but not present	Calculate BMI .bmi	-1	Applicable but not present	
	0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable	
	1	Only in SOAP Note		1	Only in SOAP Note		1	Only in SOAP Note	
	2	In PMH tab, in SOAP note, and if significant in Pregnancy Problem list		2	In Allergies tab, in SOAP note if applicable to care, and in Pregnancy Problem list (latex, etc.)		2	In Pregnancy Problem List as "BMI at 1st visit"	
Past Surgical History .psh	-1	Applicable but not present	Current Meds	-1	Applicable but not present	Total Weight Gain .twg	-1	Applicable but not present	
	0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable	
	1	Only in SOAP Note		1	Only in SOAP Note		1	Only in SOAP Note if abnormal	
	2	In PSH tab, in SOAP note, and if significant in Pregnancy Problem list		2	In Current Meds tab, in SOAP note if applicable to care, and in Pregnancy Problem list (if applicable), should include PNVs (delete meds not used during pregnancy)		2	In SOAP note and In Pregnancy Problem List if significant (excessive/inadequate)	
Family History: .fh Specifically Hypertension, Diabetes, Heart Disease, Cancer, Bleeding/Clotting Disorders, Birth Defects	-1	Applicable but not present	Height	-1	Applicable but not present	Current Vitals .vs	-1	Applicable but not present	
	0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable	
	1	Only in SOAP Note or Incomplete		1	Only in SOAP Note		1	In OB Vitals	
	2	Complete and In FH tab, in SOAP note, and if significant in Pregnancy Problem list		2	In OB Vitals tab		2	In OB Vitals (if in expected range) In SOAP note and In Pregnancy Problem List if significant (excessive/inadequate)	
Obstetrical History	-1	Applicable but not present	Weight before pregnancy	-1	Applicable but not present	LMP .lmp	-1	Applicable but not present	
	0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable	
	1	Only in SOAP Note		1	Only in SOAP Note		1	Only in SOAP note	
	2	In PSH tab, in SOAP note, and in Pregnancy Problem list		2	In OB Vitals tab under "Pre-pregnancy" field on right		2	In dating tab, SOAP note, and Pregnancy Problem list	
Prior OB Complications	-1	Applicable but not present	Current weight	-1	Applicable but not present	Dating based on: LMP, ultrasound, prior care, other	-1	Applicable but not present	
	0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable	
	1	Only in SOAP Note		1	Only in SOAP Note		1	Only in SOAP note	
	2	In OB tab, in SOAP note, and in Pregnancy Problem list		2	In OB Vitals tab		2	In dating tab, SOAP note, and Pregnancy Problem list	

Figure 3. Peer Audit Tool Side A. Adapted from "Using a prenatal electronic medical record to improve documentation within an inner-city healthcare network," by J. Ghartey, C. Lee, E. Weinberger, L. Nathan, I. Merkatz, and P. Bernstein, 2014, *American Journal of Perinatology*. Advance online publication.

Documentation Audit Tool: First Prenatal Visit						(SIDE B)				
	Score	Description		Score	Description		Score	Description	Raw Totals	Applicable (# of Yes)
Prior Prenatal Care: transfer of care from *** at approximately *** weeks -ga	-1	Applicable but not present	Orders: Type and Rh, Indirect coombs, RPR, HIV, HbSag, Rubella, Varicella, CBC, HbA1c, UA, Urine Culture, 1 hour PG if indicated (prior GDM, macrosomia, obesity), Hemoglobin Electrophoresis (if indicated), serial beta Hcg (if indicated)	-1	Applicable but not present	Documented: Reviewed teratogen risk reduction	-1	Applicable but not present		
	0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		
	1	Only in SOAP note		1	Only in SOAP note		1	Only in SOAP note		
	2	In dating tab, SOAP note, and Pregnancy Problem list		2	In SOAP note, Orders Complete		2	In SOAP note and After Visit Summary (AVS)		
Physical Assessment (minimal of thyroid, heart, lungs, breasts, abdomen, gyn)	-1	Applicable but not present or	Documented: Reviewed danger s/s bleeding, pain, hyperemesis	-1	Applicable but not present	Documented: Follow up Appointment	-1	Applicable but not present		
	0	Not Applicable (recent exam with this pregnancy)		0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		
	1	Only in SOAP note		1	Only in SOAP note		1	Only in SOAP note		
	2	Complete, In SOAP note, and if any significant Findins also in Pregnancy Problem list		2	In SOAP note and After Visit Summary (AVS)		2	Per department guidelines, and in Pregnancy Problem list if indicated		
Physical Assessment: Ultrasound	-1	Applicable but not present or	Documented: Reviewed nutrition, expected weight gain	-1	Applicable but not present	Referrals: Genetics if ≥ 35 or Hx indicated MFM if hx indicated (hx 1st degree relative with congenital anomalies, prior pregnancy	-1	Applicable but not present		
	0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		0	Not Applicable		
	1	Only in SOAP note		1	Only in SOAP note		1	Only in SOAP note		
	2	In SOAP note, in dating tab and if any significant Findings also in Pregnancy Problem list		2	In SOAP note and After Visit Summary (AVS)		2	Per department guidelines, in SOAP note and in Pregnancy Problem list if indicated		
Prenatal screening option discussion	-1	Applicable but not present	Auditor's comments for this document						Total of Sides A & B	# Applicable Items Sides A & B
	0	Not Applicable								
	1	Only in SOAP note								
	2	In SOAP note, and if decided: Pregnancy Problem list, and prior testing results if applicable (transfer of care)								
Reviewer Comments for document									Average of Sides A & B	

Figure 4. Peer Audit Tool Side B. Adapted from “Using a prenatal electronic medical record to improve documentation within an inner-city healthcare network,” by J. Ghartey, C. Lee, E. Weinberger, L. Nathan, I. Merkatz, and P. Bernstein, 2014, *American Journal of Perinatology*. Advance online publication.

Documentation Audits

Benefits Associated with Audits

While considering documentation audits as a strategy to improve documentation quality, factors that may strengthen or weaken the findings of the audits were the focus for this literature search. Several studies credit documentation audits with improving not only documentation, but also care delivered (Elder, McEwen, Flach, Gallimore, & Pallerla, 2010; Gharney et al., 2014; Gitkind, Perla, Manno, & Klugman, 2014; Kamath et al., 2012; Milchak et al., 2012; Staton, Kraemer, Patel, Talente, & Estrada, 2007). Elder et al. (2010) found that results were better managed in charts that had complete documentation, while Kamath et al. (2012) found more reliable gestational age documentation when audits were performed.

Physician residents who performed documentation audits of peers increased actual care performance (Staton et al., 2007). When residents were asked to perform chart audits of diabetics, subsequent audits found not only improved documentation, but also more complete care delivery. The residents began to perform the necessary examinations in order to complete the documentation found within the audits. They credited the teaching tool of performance of documentation audits with more success than any other teaching method including lectures and demonstrations.

In a grounded theory study with 13 peer coaches involving quality audits, Sekerka and Chao (2003) found that peer coaching in a Department of Family Medicine fostered professional development for those who do the coaching, as well as those who receive the coaching. Themes pulled from the data centered on personal learning and growth, positive self-assessment and improved ability to see bigger picture (Sekerka & Chao, 2003).

Gitkind et al. (2014) provide evidence for continued assessment of documentation within the EMR in order to improve documentation standards. They identified the need for ongoing strategies for QI, but from “top-down” participation. When department administrators were engaged and participated, documentation audits sustained improvements over time. By incorporating strategies of documentation audits into daily work, Gitkind et al. (2014) found high levels of awareness, compliance, and subsequent QI.

Costs Associated with Audits

As with many strategies, there are often associated costs. Eisenberg, Cunningham, Siewert, and Kruskal (2014) evaluated the views of radiologists who participated in the peer audit process. Half agreed that audits improved performance, and one third attributed audits to decreased medical errors. However, in that same group, 44% found audits to be a waste of time, and 58% were under the impression that audits were only done to meet hospital or regulatory requirements. It is important to note that each radiologist was expected to review a number of cases equivalent to 2.5% of their annual caseload, with 300 cases as the maximum limit. Within this study, radiologists acknowledged that this heavy caseload contributed to not only their attitudes toward the audits, but also the thoroughness used in the audit.

Eisenberg et al. (2014) also found that the audited peer often felt a bias in the selection for auditors and types of cases audited. They indicated that “relatively little attention is paid to analyzing the reasons for errors leading to efforts to improve performance” (p. 5). Rather than focusing on documentation errors, they stress the need to facilitate education by sharing mistakes encountered in the audits. They underline that the

intent of peer audit is to improve the performance of all, not only those who are found to have errors, or inadequacies.

Performing audits takes time. The culture of the system has to embrace the aspect of worth for the learning in order for the audits to be sustainable. Chang and Mark (2011) found that when errors or inadequacies are discovered, much could be learned by sharing those findings within the team. If the team owns the inadequacies, rather than attributing them to specific individuals, then the whole team can address specific issues, and mentor each other. While there is a cost of time for performing documentation audits, an environment that embraces its importance may find that the time savings by improved documentation may actually override the time required for the audits (Ghartey et al., 2014).

Kirkendall, Goldenhar, Simon, Wheeler, and Andrew Spooner (2013) found the need to provide continued assessment of documentation quality. In their 12-month study, as time progressed they found a decrease in documentation quality. The risk for this was significantly higher with the introduction of new documentation strategies based on the assumption that prior implementations continued to be used correctly. Gitkind et al. (2014) expressed the same concerns and stressed that audits should be part of daily functioning in order to maintain quality.

Conclusion

Documentation audits must be viewed as improving care, and as having the potential to save time in the health care setting. Documentation audits should be regarded as learning tools, and not a review of any single person's performance. A team approach to audits has demonstrated increased learning benefits. The requested workload has to be

commensurate with the anticipated benefits, and the findings have to be shared in order to improve the performance of all.

Error Discovery

Potential Types of Error

Since the publication of *To Err is Human*, many changes have occurred in healthcare to facilitate root cause analyses and strategies to create internal non-punitive error reporting systems, as well as to protect reporting of non-serious medical errors (Institute of Medicine, 2000). At the time of the Institute of Medicine (IOM) publication, adverse events occurred in 3.7% of all hospitalizations, with 13.6% of these resulting in death. More than two-thirds were found to be preventable.

IOM (2000) found four major types of medical errors: diagnostic, treatment, preventive, and “other” types. When a diagnostic error takes place, it can result in an error or delay in diagnosis, failure to employ indicated tests, use of outmoded tests or therapy, or failure to act on results of monitoring or testing (IOM, 2000). The second type of error presented within the IOM study focused on treatment, or errors “in the performance of an operation, procedure or test . . . administering the treatment . . . dose or method of using a drug . . . avoidable delay in treatment or responding to an abnormal test . . . inappropriate (not indicated) care” (IOM, 2000, p. 36). While reminiscent of the first category, the third category focuses on failure to provide preventative care: either failing to provide adequate prophylactic treatment, or providing inadequate monitoring or follow up of that treatment. Failure of communication, equipment and systems failures comprise the final “other” category presented by the IOM (2000).

Participation in Audit and Error Discovery

Errors discovered during a QI project are considered “protected” and do not require reporting (Gitkind et al., 2014), which encourages participation in the process. Historically, medical errors were hidden behind closed doors, often with those closest to the error completely unaware (Linthorst, Kallimanis-King, Douwes Dekker, Hoekstra, & de Haes, 2012). Wu, Cavanaugh, McPhee, Lo, and Micco (1997, p. 770) define a medical mistake as “a commission or an omission with potentially negative consequences for the patient that would have been judged wrong by skilled and knowledgeable peers at the time it occurred, independent of whether there were any negative consequences.” Linthorst et al. (2012) posit that developing departmental cultures of discussing medical errors in a non-judgmental, safe environment is crucial to improve reporting of medical errors.

Ethics of Error Reporting

According to Devettere and (2010), the morally reasonable thing to do or not do, is also the ethical thing to do or not do. While remembering the principles of practice-autonomy, beneficence, justice and non-maleficence-we can consider what is ethical in dealing with a discovered medical error. Will the patient benefit or be harmed by being informed of the error? Patients generally want to know when an error has occurred in their care. Fein et al. (2007) found that patients want a clear, understandable explanation of errors, with an apology and a plan to avoid future errors.

Error disclosure: The patient. Fein et al. (2007) identified six components of disclosure in a qualitative study. They include disclosure admission, discussion of the event, a link to the proximal event, a discussion of the proximal event, a link to the harm,

and finally identification of the harm. Here is an example containing all of the elements for a patient, who, after becoming hypoglycemic, suffered a seizure, fell out of bed, and broke a hip:

Your hip broke. The reason for that was that your sugar was low, and the reason that your sugar fell so low was because you did not have any food and the medication was not withheld. It was an error, and unfortunately you had a bad outcome. (Fein et al., 2007, p. 757)

They also provide a definition of error disclosure:

Error disclosure = Communication between a health care provider and a patient, family members, or the patient's proxy that acknowledges the occurrence of an error, discusses what happened, and describes the link between the error and outcomes in a manner that is meaningful to the patient. (Fein et al., 2006, p. 760)

Error disclosure: The provider. Medical errors produce additional casualties, as health care providers involved in errors also become victims. Wu (2000) describes the situation as one where the provider agonizes over the error and is torn between confessing and the dread of the potential outcome created by the confession.

When sharing the errors of others, one feels less exposed and able to face guilt (Wu, 2000). Without the opportunity to face the guilt they have experienced, the provider may turn to dysfunctional coping methods. This contributes heavily to patterns of "burn out," loss of self-confidence, and a potential downward distress spiral. Wu (2000) provides strategies for assisting colleagues who have made an error. First, he emphasizes the need to place ourselves in that person's place. We should create a safe environment to discuss completely what happened without minimizing the gravity. Discussion of

disclosure of the mistake needs to be included. Once completing the difficult task of sharing the error with the patient, the provider can then move through the healing steps of acknowledgement, to steps that prevent the error's reoccurrence. At that point, the provider can use problem solving techniques to explore circumstances that contributed to the problem, identify what could be done differently, and explore individual and institutional level changes that can reduce the risk of the error recurrence.

Current NHCS Error Reporting Policies

As with many large healthcare agencies, the NHCS has developed and placed all of its policies on a central internal website available to employees. The policies used for this project are specific to the local area. The section for Risk Management and Patient Safety provides policies addressing error discovery and management (Kaiser Permanente, 2014b).

The policy "Handling and Reporting of Unusual Occurrences" applies to patients in both outpatient and inpatient settings. It provides a clear definition of what constitutes an "Unusual Occurrence" (UO), as well as step-by-step management guidance. Examples of UOs are defined as untoward occurrences or accidents, undesirable deviation from usual practices, out of ordinary events that involve risk or actual injury to an individual, or damage to property. Also reportable are "near misses" or situations that could have resulted in injury or illness, but did not because of intervention. Appropriate reporting forms for each type of category are available online and are submitted upon completion (Kaiser Permanente, 2014b).

The stated purpose for this type of reporting system is to provide a safe environment by focusing on system problems or issues rather than on individuals. It

provides a method to identify, document and report occurrences throughout the Medical Centers and Outpatient areas creating a centralized database. With this database, patterns of risk are identified and corrective actions can be taken to reduce those risks. It also establishes a system for reporting that is protected from discoverability by utilizing attorney-client privilege (Kaiser Permanente, 2014b).

In the event of an UO the attending provider is contacted and notified. The provider then examines the patient, provides prompt and proper care as deemed necessary. All care, including actions to alleviate an injury, and patient response to treatment, is documented in the medical record. The provider is also responsible for preserving evidence, such as documents or supplies, to ensure an effective analysis and record of the occurrence. Statements from witnesses may be gathered.

The patient and, if indicated, the family, are informed of care outcomes, including unanticipated adverse outcomes. The NHCS Situation Management Team is available for support and consultation, and coordinates the communication process. Available through the hospital operator, this team consists of representatives from the medical group, administration, risk management, quality management, legal counsel, and public affairs departments.

Once the patient's immediate needs are met, an "Unusual Occurrence Report" (UOR) is completed and submitted online (Kaiser Permanente, 2014b). The UOR goes to the Department Administrator who has seven days to complete and submit the management investigation report to the Risk Management Department. Risk Management reviews the case for legal implications, and sends it to the Peer Review Committee (PRC). This committee is comprised of approximately 4-6 peer physicians and 2-3 peer advanced

practice providers. A designated peer reviews the medical record, contacts persons involved, and reviews case-specific policies and current literature. The designated peer then presents the case to the PRC. The PRC determines whether the care provided met standards and the event was unavoidable, or within the anticipated risks for the care or procedure; or was avoidable and a result of the care provided.

Any provider can request a case review, as well as Membership services in response to patient complaints. Additionally, all cases submitted to Risk Management are reviewed. The PRC can address concerns discovered during EMR audits (Kaiser Permanente, 2014b).

Conclusion

As documentation of the EMRs involves not only reviewing the records for quality, but presents the possibility of finding actual errors in the care provided, there is an ethical responsibility to address those errors. As Devetterre (2010) discussed, the ethical thing to do is also the morally correct thing to do. Fein (2007) presented that patients want to know why things happen when there are unexpected outcomes. Along with the patient, we have to consider the provider's role, not only who provided the care, but the provider who discovers the error. The system as established within the NHCS appropriately addresses these issues, and provides a method to manage errors discovered through documentation audits.

Review of Literature Conclusion

The review of the literature yielded information that contributed to the implementation of the Documentation Audit as a method for QI. The findings established which key aspects of PNC should be considered for evaluation in the first Audit Tool.

Information regarding the use of documentation audits provided a framework for the process. There must be enough audits completed to yield the information regarding adequacy and accuracy of documentation, but not so many that providers considered the task to be excessive and onerous. Using a team approach with adequate post audit briefings has the potential to maximize learning, and subsequent improved documentation. Finally, the local evidence reviewed indicates that NHCS has a system in place that addresses the potential concerns of error discovery.

METHODS

Ethical Considerations

Asking peers to audit patient EMRs involved several aspects that required consideration of potential ethical concerns. The first was how to handle error discovery either in documentation or in care provided. As errors in either can affect health care outcomes, team members shared an established method for managing error discovery.

Since the study involved perceptions of participation in a documentation audit by the CNMs, requests for review were made to the Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) of both the large NHCS, as well as California State University, Fullerton. The project was granted exempt status following these reviews. As the documentation audits were part of a QI project, they were not subject to review.

Documentation Audit Error Discovery

While findings of a QI are protected, we do have the potential for error discovery. Ethically, we were required to address any error, especially when immediate care could correct or minimize its potential outcome. As an audit team, we discussed and developed a formalized method to address such abnormalities. Potential errors ranged from simple omissions, to actual errors in documentation, or errors in clinical practice.

As the EMRs being audited belonged to patients who were currently pregnant, updating and correcting the records was essential for ensuring appropriate care for the remainder of the pregnancy. Actual errors were corrected in the same manner as omissions. These were tracked as audit team “near misses,” and submitted in a report to the Peer Review Team. This was done for two reasons: (a) so the Peer Review Team was apprised of the “near misses”; and (b) so our administrative team was kept informed as to

the Audit Team progress. When errors were found that directly affected care, the UOR process was followed.

Participation in Documentation Audit Study

Prior to orientation of the documentation audit process, all qualifying members of the CNM service were asked to participate in the study regarding their baseline and post-participation knowledge and attitudes and learning. The survey invitation contained wording that the participant gave implied consent via survey completion.

Participants

During early fall 2014, all CNM team members ($N = 15$) who see patients in the office and as well as practice in the hospital were invited to participate and chose to do so. The CNMs were women educated in the western United States. Licensed in California and certified by the American Midwifery Certification Board (AMCB), they held Drug Enforcement Agency (DEA) prescription furnishing licenses. They ranged in age from 32 to 68 years, and had been practicing Midwifery between 4 and 29 years for a large Health Maintenance Organization (HMO). They provided full scope women's health care, and as a team delivered over 70,000 babies since 1980.

Instruments

Two tools were developed. The first was the audit tool for used for auditing the EMRs, and the second was the survey used to evaluate CNM perceptions of the documentation audit experience.

Audit Tool: Peer Audit Tool (PAT)

This prototype audit tool was developed based on standards for PNC. These standards were established from the literature review and published guidelines. While the care delivery schedule from NHCS was utilized, practice recommendations from the

WHO, NIH, CDC, ACOG and ACNM professional agencies, as well as the NHCS, were integrated into this tool.

The prenatal audit tool developed by Gharthey et al. (2014) evaluated the adequacy of documentation of Prenatal Care. Gharthey and colleagues compared prenatal paper documentations to electronic documentations. They evaluated components relative to prenatal documentation including past medical history, substance use screening, family history with comments regarding inheritable disorders, psychosocial screening, initial physical exam, Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) counseling and testing, triple screen testing or referral for amniocentesis, level II ultrasound results if indicated, gestational diabetes screening results; and fundal height (FH) and fetal heart rate (FHR) at all visits after the first trimester.

Our peer audit tool (PAT) (Figure 3), incorporated those elements from the Gharthey tool, but were specific to our EMR system. The PAT reflected not only the standards of PNC, but also specified where the documentation should be located in the EMR. The first audit focused on documentation of new prenatal patients and contained 25 data points of the PAT within various locations of the EMR.

Documented elements included personal medical history, review of surgical history, obstetrical history, and a review of family history including bleeding and clotting disorders, congenital anomalies, and other birth complications. Additional components included prenatal laboratory tests, office dating ultrasound, counseling of testing options, and education in prenatal danger signs/symptoms to report, nutritional needs, and teratogen risk reduction. The EMR was also assessed for adequate orders, follow-up appointments, and referrals as indicated.

For scoring, a documentation quality index (DQI) was calculated to provide an objective method to assess adequacy and appropriate placement. Table 1 demonstrates the values assigned for each audited element of prenatal care; adding the values for all elements generated a raw score in accordance with scoring described by Gharthey et al. (2014). A score of 0 indicates that the element was not applicable to this patient and did not affect the overall score. The raw score divided by the number of applicable items for the patient produces the DQI. In Table 2, two examples are provided for the computation of the DQI. If the total number of items is 19 and all are adequately documented and in the right location, the resulting raw score is 38 points. Divide the raw score by 19 applicable items results in a DQI of 2.

Table 1

PAT Scoring System

Missing needed documentation	Documentation not needed for this patient	Documentation present but incomplete or in wrong location	Documentation adequate and in correct location
-1	0	+1	+2

Note. Adapted from “Using a prenatal electronic medical record to improve documentation within an inner-city healthcare network,” by J. Gharthey, C. Lee, E. Weinberger, L. Nathan, I. Merkatz, and P. Bernstein, 2014, *American Journal of Perinatology*. Advance online publication.

An example is the patient who presented for her first visit later in the pregnancy, and was not a candidate for many of the initial screens for the first trimester. Her overall raw score for 12 items was 24, making the DQI 2 ($24 / 12 = 2$). However, if 8 items were correctly documented (+16), and two items were documented but incomplete (+2), and another two applicable items were missing (-2), the total raw score would be 16. Dividing

the raw score by 12 applicable items produces a DQI score of 1.33. This method allowed us to adjust the number of items included within the audit without affecting the score.

Table 2

Documentation Quality Index (DQI) Computation

Pt A presents at 8 weeks	Pt. B presents at 25 weeks
19 applicable items	12 applicable items
All 19 items adequately documented and in right location (38 points)	8 adequately documented items and in right location (16 points) 2 items documented but in wrong location (2 points) 2 applicable items not addressed (-2 points)
38 points/19 items = DQI 2.0	16 points/12 items = DQI 1.33

Note. Adapted from “Using a prenatal electronic medical record to improve documentation within an inner-city healthcare network,” by J. Ghartey, C. Lee, E. Weinberger, L. Nathan, I. Merkatz, and P. Bernstein, 2014, *American Journal of Perinatology*. Advance online publication.

Survey: Peer Audit Learning Team (PALT) Survey

A pre and post participation survey, the Peer Audit Learning Team (PALT) survey, was designed to assess the perceptions of Learning, Reluctance, and Time in participating in documentation audits (Appendix B). This 31-item survey with Likert-type responses was modified from a study of radiologist perceptions of audits (Eisenberg, 2014). The PALT Survey explores factors that may enhance or hinder QI project participation. It helps to identify those perceived to contribute to learning from the audit process, reluctance of participation, and perceptions of worthwhileness of time involved.

- *Learning.* Questions focused on the auditor’s perception of learning. The questions identified whether it was the actual EMR audit that afforded the

learning, the post-audit discussion, or both? Questions explored perceptions of individual learning, and learning by the whole team.

- *Reluctance.* Questions focused on perceived barriers to participation. These included fear of reprisal, fear of revealing inadequacies, and fear of revealing the inadequacies of peers. Questions also addressed fear of encountering significant errors that would need intervention.
- *Time.* Questions focused on benefit of participation versus the cost. Questions regarding the number of documentation audits and time involved provided opportunities for modifying the process for future audits.

Reluctance and Learning domain questions used a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neither disagree nor agree, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree. Some items were stated such that they were reverse coded prior to data analysis. Higher scores indicated positive attitudes and positive learning.

The domain of Time was scaled differently, evaluating the appropriateness of time/work involved. Items allowed for expression of attitudes regarding the effort required by the audit process, and whether the number of documents audited was appropriate. These questions utilized a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = extremely excessive, 2 = excessive, 3 = adequate, 4 = barely adequate, 5 = not enough. The neutral score, 3, indicated perceived appropriateness of time and energy required for the audits. The final Time item assessed estimated amount of time in minutes for each documentation audit.

At the end of the PALT survey, there was a section for suggestions that allowed participants to suggest modifications to the documentation audit process and suggestions

for future documentation audit topics. Process modifications and recommendations for content selection for future audits considered these comments.

Procedures

Audit Process: Use of the PAT

Preparation. The audit process consisted of a pre audit orientation to the audit process and use of the PAT, a group sample audit utilizing the PAT, random selection of CNMs to audit, audit completion, presentation of the findings, and two post audit debriefing sessions.

During a regularly scheduled team meeting, CNMs were oriented to the audit process and trained in the use of the PAT. Together, they audited a sample medical record. Criteria were presented for what comprised appropriate documentation, either in adequacy or location, along with tool scoring. Also discussed were potential error discovery and management processes as established by the NHCS. Personal instruction was provided to three CNMs who were not at the meeting.

Audits. Each CNM (CNM 1) randomly drew the name of another CNM (CNM 2) whose documentation she audited. CNM1 then accessed the last 8 weeks of the schedule, and randomly selected the first five initial PNC visits documentations for a convenience sample from CNM2's schedule. CNM1 then completed the audit tool for each those five EMRs, evaluating the 25 items of the PAT within the EMR. For the initial audit, each CNM1 audited five medical records. This number of audit documentations was deemed sufficient to reflect CNM documentation patterns, and yet not excessive enough to be "burdensome." The initial estimate of the time needed to complete each of the five audits was approximately 20 minutes, or a total of 1 hour, 40 minutes.

Post-audit Debriefings. Audit findings were shared with the team over the next two subsequent monthly meetings during post audit debriefing sessions. Only CNM1s knew the names of CNM2s, and only aggregate scores without CNM identifiers were shared. This allowed CNMs approximately two months to select and complete the five audits. Those who were already competent, whether consciously or unconsciously, shared tips for working within the system, and mentored the team as a whole. Promoting a shared learning environment based on our PAL framework was utilized in the hope to benefit the team as a whole, rather than singling out those whose documentation was less than adequate. As many CNMs were found to be competent documenters, they shared tricks or tips that could effectively achieve adequate documentation with efficiency. Since the exchange of information occurred within the QI forum, the post audit debriefing discussion was protected. This encouraged participation without fear.

Future Audits. We plan to repeat the audit process of the initial PNC visit in three months (post-doctoral project) to evaluate whether documentation quality changed. The overall DQI scores of the first audit will be compared with those of the second audit. The overall scores will be used rather than individual scores since this will show the benefit of participation by the whole team.

If the repeat of the audit process demonstrates improving documentation, we will ask management for their ongoing support of audits. Within this framework, audits could have foci not only on documentation, but also on other aspects of care. For instance, if we find new evidence pointing to the need for a change in our current practice, we could then use this audit process.

Survey Process: PALT Survey

CNMs completed the PALT surveys at baseline (prior to the audit orientation) and after the audit process completion (following the final debriefing session). Each PALT survey took less than 10 minutes to complete, and responses were kept confidential. CNMs read consent forms, and completed surveys prior to orientation to the use of the PAT. The post audit survey took place two months after the initial survey and after the second debriefing session during the CNM meeting.

Data Analysis**Audits: PAT**

The data from the five documentation audits per CNM were evaluated using the DQI method. The aggregate average for the whole team and averages for each of the 25 items were generated in first audit (completed December 2014 - January 2015) of the initial PNC visits. Descriptive statistics were used with Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Only aggregate averages for the 25 items as well as the combined scores were used.

The post project goal is to complete the second audit (currently in progress) and compare prenatal DQI scores to the first scores. This audit cycle is being conducted with a rotation of auditors. Rotating auditors minimizes the effect of bias for the second auditor, as she will not know the first audit results for that CNM. Post project, the average total scores from the first and second audits will be compared with paired *t*-test analysis to assess whether significant differences occur.

Surveys: PALT Surveys

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze demographic data using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Mean scores and standard deviations (M , SD) were calculated for each of the three domains of Learning, Reluctance, and Time and for individual items from the pre and post-audit PALT surveys with paired samples t -tests.

RESULTS

Peer Documentation Audits: PAT

The CNM team ($N = 15$) completed 51 audits, with each midwife completing between three and five audits. The team audited the records of women entering care at gestational ages between 5 weeks 3 days and 35 weeks 3 days, with the average age of approximately 9 weeks. Table 3 displays the results of the first audit focused on the documentation of the initial prenatal visit.

If all records were complete, accurate, and documented items in the appropriate location, a DQI score of 2.00 would be the result. The average composite score resulted in the DQI score of 1.44 for the team. This indicates that some areas either lacked information, or were not in the expected areas of the EMR specific to prenatal care.

Reviewing the specific items within the audit, no area demonstrated complete compliance. Prenatal orders documentation had a near perfect DQI score of 1.96. The lowest score was for documentation of teratogen risk reduction (0.08). While this is a standard component of prenatal care, it was rarely documented. A DQI score of -1 indicated that the information was expected to be found within the EMR based on the patient's prenatal status and yet was not discovered anywhere in the documentation by the auditor. As seen in Table 3, there were 19 items that had at least one score of -1 (meaning that in at least one EMR, the CNM failed to document this or that documentation was not discoverable). Five items resulted in average DQI scores of < 1 : weight prior to pregnancy (0.88), total weight gain (0.49), prior prenatal care (0.31), review of teratogen risks (0.08), and indicated referrals (0.67).

Table 3

Initial Prenatal Care Visit Documentation Audit Results

First Prenatal Audit Results					
	<i>n</i>	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	<i>SD</i>
Approximate Gestational Age when entered care	51	5.3	35.3	9.24	5.26
Audit Average DQI Score	51	0.60	2.00	1.44	0.26
Past Medical History	51	-1.00	2.00	1.92	0.44
Past Surgical History	51	-1.00	2.00	1.90	0.46
Family History	51	-1.00	2.00	1.86	0.50
Obstetrical History	51	-1.00	2.00	1.51	0.88
Prior Obstetrical Complications	51	0.00	2.00	1.08	1.00
Allergies	51	-1.00	2.00	1.59	1.00
Current Medications	51	-1.00	2.00	1.26	1.22
Height	51	-1.00	2.00	1.76	0.65
Weight Prior to Pregnancy	51	-1.00	2.00	0.88	1.41
Current Weight	51	-1.00	2.00	1.90	0.46
Body Mass Index	51	-1.00	2.00	1.69	0.79
Total Weight Gain	51	-1.00	2.00	0.49	0.91
Current Vital Signs	51	1.00	2.00	1.94	0.24
Last Menstrual Period	51	-1.00	2.00	1.75	0.63
Dating Source	51	-1.00	2.00	1.82	0.65
Prior Prenatal Care	51	0.00	2.00	0.31	0.74
Physical Assessment	51	2.00	2.00	2.00	0.00
Physical Assessment: Ultrasound	51	-1.00	2.00	1.78	0.64
Discussion of Prenatal Screening	51	-1.00	2.00	1.37	1.00
Prenatal Care Orders	51	1.00	2.00	1.96	0.20
Review of Reportable Danger Signs and Symptom	51	-1.00	2.00	1.26	1.07
Review of Nutrition/Expected Weight Gain Based on BMI	51	-1.00	2.00	1.18	0.87
Review of Teratogen Risk Reduction	51	-1.00	2.00	0.08	1.20
Follow Up Appointment	51	1.00	2.00	1.98	0.14
Referrals as Indicated	51	-1.00	2.00	0.67	1.01

Note. Adapted from “Using a prenatal electronic medical record to improve documentation within an inner-city healthcare network,” by J. Gartey, C. Lee, E. Weinberger, L. Nathan, I. Merkatz, and P. Bernstein, 2014, *American Journal of Perinatology*. Advance online publication.

Surveys: PALT Surveys

Demographics

The entire CNM team ($N = 15$) participated in the pre-post audit surveys and EMR documentation audits during fall 2014. As seen in Table 4, all 15 CNM participants were women, educated in California with English as a primary language, and ranged in age from >30 to >60 years. A majority of CNMs (14 of 15; 93%) self-rated their pre-employment computer skills as either “good” or “excellent.” One rated herself as having minimal skills, or “I knew what a mouse and email were.”

PALT Surveys: Learning, Reluctance and Time

No statistically significant changes were found between baseline and post-audit average total scores for each of the two domain scores of perceptions of Learning and Time. In the domain of Reluctance, CNM perception significantly decreased following the audit experience, meaning that CNMs were less reluctant to participate in documentation, ($p < .001$). These results can be seen in Tables 5-7.

Table 4

Demographics of Survey Participants

Characteristic	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Female	15	100.0
Age in years		
> 30, < 40	3	20.0
> 40, < 50	3	20.0
> 50, < 60	6	40.0
> 60	3	20.0
Length of time as health care provider in obstetrics/gynecology		
> 5 years, < 10 years	3	20.0
>10 years, < 15 years	1	6.7
> 15	11	73.3
Length of time with this obstetrical/gynecological midwifery team		
2 - 5 years	2	13.3
> 5 years, < 10 years	3	20.0
> 10 years, < 15 years	2	13.3
> 15 years	8	53.3
Language spoken to as child		
English	15	100.0
Language of primary education		
English	15	100.0
State of obstetrical/gynecological midwifery training		
California	15	100.0
Self- rated computer skills prior to this position		
Minimal: I knew what a mouse and email were	1	6.7
Good: I was able to function and navigate the computer systems after orientation	8	53.3
Excellent: I was able to help others with trouble shooting problems	6	40.0

Note. *N* = 15.

Table 5

Learning Perception Survey Results

Survey Results Categorized by Learning	Pre Audit <i>M (SD)</i>	Post Audit <i>M (SD)</i>	<i>p</i> - value ^a
Domain of Learning Average	4.08 (0.44)	4.30 (0.39)	.10
1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree			
1. My documentation is accurate.	4.20 (0.56)	3.87 (0.74)	.24
2. My documentation is complete.	3.93 (0.59)	3.80 (0.68)	.58
3. My documentation is in the appropriate place in the EMR.	4.07 (1.03)	4.13 (0.64)	.75
4. Documentation audits decrease medical errors.	3.47 (1.30)	4.20 (1.08)	.05
5. I learn as I evaluate the documentation of my peers.	4.53 (0.64)	4.53 (1.06)	1.00
6. I learn by discussing our documentation audits.	4.53 (0.64)	4.67 (0.72)	.50
7. I will experience satisfaction by completing this documentation audit.	4.00 (0.76)	4.13 (0.64)	.63
8. Others will learn by discussing our documentation audits.	4.20 (0.68)	4.74 (0.46)	.03
9. My ability to provide care is affected by the quality/adequacy of others' documentation.	4.53 (0.74)	4.47 (1.06)	.79
10. My documentation will improve by participating in Documentation Audits.	4.33 (0.49)	4.73 (0.46)	.03
11. My care will improve by participating in documentation audits.	4.13 (0.74)	4.53 (0.74)	.11
12. My ability to provide care will improve by whole team participation in the documentation audit process	4.13 (0.64)	4.53 (0.64)	.05
13. Others will experience satisfaction by completing this documentation audit.	3.80 (0.78)	3.93 (0.70)	.55
14. Others will learn by evaluating the documentation of peers.	4.27 (0.59)	4.60 (0.51)	.10
15. The documentation of my peers is accurate, complete and in the appropriate place.	3.20 (0.68)	3.53 (0.74)	.21
16. The documentation of others will improve.	3.87 (0.92)	4.47 (0.52)	.02

Note. Questions adapted from "Survey of Faculty Perceptions Regarding a Peer Review System" by R. Eisenberg, M. Cunningham, B. Siewert, and J. Kruskal, 2014, *Journal of the American College of Radiology*, 11(4), 397–401.

N = 15.

^a for paired *t*-tests.

Table 6

Reluctance Perception Survey Results

Survey Results Categorized by Reluctance	Pre Audit <i>M (SD)</i>	Post Audit <i>M (SD)</i>	<i>p</i> - value ^a
Domain of Reluctance Average	2.41 (0.37)	2.04 (0.25)	.00
1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree			
1. Documentation audits are a waste of time.	1.40 (0.51)	1.40 (0.51)	1.00
2. Documentation audits are done only to meet hospital and regulatory compliance.	1.73 (1.10)	1.40 (0.51)	.33
3. I am afraid a significant error could be found in my care or documentation during audit of my documentation.	2.73 (1.10)	3.20 (1.02)	.26
4. I am afraid I could be disciplined by having my documentation audited.	3.13 (0.99)	2.27 (1.10)	.01
5. I am afraid I will find a significant error in my peer's care or documentation.	3.20 (0.56)	3.13 (0.92)	.79
6. I consciously select less time intensive cases to audit.	2.73 (0.59)	1.93 (0.70)	.00
7. I enter an audit rating without reviewing the documentation.	1.73 (0.80)	1.40 (0.63)	.14
8. I only participate in documentation audits because I feel forced or obliged to participate.	2.13 (1.13)	2.00 (0.76)	.25
9. If I detect an error or problem in documentation as I audit, I tend to score on the side of <i>under-rating</i> the error.	2.53 (0.74)	1.87 (0.83)	.04
10. If I detect an error or problem in the documentation, I tend to score on the side of <i>over-rating</i> the error.	2.80 (0.41)	1.80 (1.01)	.00

Note. Questions adapted from "Survey of Faculty Perceptions Regarding a Peer Review System" by R. Eisenberg, M. Cunningham, B. Siewert, and J. Kruskal, 2014, *Journal of the American College of Radiology*, 11(4), 397–401.

N = 15.

^a for paired *t*-tests.

Table 7

Time Perception Survey Results

Survey Results Categorized by Time	Pre Audit <i>M (SD)</i>	Post Audit <i>M (SD)</i>	<i>p</i> - value ^a
Domain of Time Average	2.98 (0.37)	2.08 (0.39)	.26
1 = Not enough, 2 = Barely adequate, 3 = Adequate, 4 = Excessive, 5 = Extremely excessive			
1. For learning, the number of medical records I audit is	2.53 (0.99)	3.07 (0.26)	.06
2. The time required to audit each medical record is	3.13 (0.35)	2.67 (0.98)	.77
3. Four weeks to audit five medical records is	3.13 (0.64)	2.40 (0.63)	.00
4. The effort to audit each medical record is	3.13 (0.64)	3.06 (0.46)	.25
5. Each medical record audit took me approximately _____ minutes.	24.00(13.52)	30.67 (12.08)	.26

Note. Questions adapted from “Survey of Faculty Perceptions Regarding a Peer Review System” by R. Eisenberg, M. Cunningham, B. Siewert and J. Kruskal, 2014, *Journal of the American College of Radiology*, 11(4), 397–401.

N = 15.

^a for paired *t*-tests.

Examination of baseline and post-audit scores for the individual items within each domain leads to more information about specific changes within each domain. As seen in Table 5, within the domain of Learning, three of the 16 items decreased: perceptions of accuracy and completeness within personal documentation; and the ability to provide care affected by the quality/adequacy of the documentation of others. All 13 of the other items increased post audit. The greatest learning increases were seen in perceptions that documentation audits improved the documentation for self and others, enhanced learning, increased ability to provide care, and had the potential to decrease medical errors.

The items within the Reluctance domain assessed factors such as fear of reprisal or error discovery and are shown in Table 6. While 14 of 15 reluctance scores dropped or stayed the same, an increase was seen in “fear of having a significant finding either in care or documentation of care” through the audit process. However, the fear of being

disciplined for audit findings dropped significantly ($p = .01$). Three items in the Reluctance domain changed significantly, indicating CNMs were actually reviewing documents as instructed, attempting to meet the criteria as described within the tool; these items related to not under-rating or over-rating errors and not selecting less time intensive cases to audit. The results also suggested that respondents did not view audits as a waste of time, nor were they done to meet compliance standards, as CNMs either disagreed or strongly disagreed with these statements both pre and post audit.

As seen in Table 7, responses in perception to Time demonstrate that CNMs felt that the number of audits were adequate, while the amount of time to complete all five audits was considered inadequate ($p < .001$). The amount of time actually needed for the audits was greater than the estimate before the process began. As seen in Table 8, reported time needed for completing each of the five audits ranged from 10 minutes to 45 minutes, with the average time of just over 30 minutes.

Table 8

Perceived Time and Actual Time Needed for Each Audit

Time in Minutes Needed for Each Audit	<i>n</i>	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	<i>SD</i>
Perceived Time Pre-Audit	15	10.00	60.00	24.00	13.52
Actual Time Post Audit	15	10.00	45.00	30.67	12.08

Comparisons of the three domains: Learning, Reluctance and Time, can be seen in Figure 4, while the comparison of perceived time needed and actual time needed for the audit completion can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Comparison of Means of Domains of Learning, Reluctance and Time Survey adapted from “Survey of Faculty Perceptions Regarding a Peer Review System” by R. Eisenberg, M. Cunningham, B. Siewert and J. Kruskal, 2014, *Journal of the American College of Radiology*, 11(4), 397–401. Likert Scale for Learning and Reluctance: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree. Likert Scale for Time: 1 = Not enough, 2 = Barely adequate, 3 = Adequate, 4 = Excessive, 5 = Extremely excessive.

Figure 5. Perceived Time Needed to Complete Audit Compared to Actual Average Time Needed. N = 51 audits.

Summarizing the results of the participation surveys, the domain of Learning demonstrated an increase in scores, while those of Reluctance and Time decreased.

Actual time needed to complete each audit increased from what was anticipated

DISCUSSION

In this doctoral project, a QI project involving an audit process program was developed, implemented, and partly evaluated in a group of CNMs practicing in a large healthcare system in southern California. Additionally, perceptions about this process were studied. The findings are in accordance of the concepts contained within the theoretical framework of Peer Audit Learning (PAL). Results suggest raised CNM awareness of the need for documentation improvement, achieved through audit participation.

Prior to the audit process, most CNMs perceived that their documentation was complete, accurate, and in the correct place of the EMR. Many discovered that their perceptions were, in fact, at least partly in error. Post-audit survey scores indicate many CNMs may have moved from unconscious incompetence to either conscious incompetence (becomes aware of inadequacy), or conscious competence. Survey findings revealed areas that could hinder audit participation: fear of discipline, fear of error discovery within individual or peer documentation, and barriers related to the element of time. Areas that trended positively in post audit, suggesting improved participation or learning, included the ability to improve care delivery, and learning through shared discussion.

The finding that average PALT scores showed changes in the expected directions supports the PAL theoretical model. That is, the aggregate score for the domain of Learning demonstrated an increase after completion of the audit process and average scores for Reluctance and Time decreased. In fact, Reluctance demonstrated an overall significant decrease.

Results Related to Learning

When evaluating specific items in Learning the findings were consistent with the PAL theoretical framework. Through audit participation CNMs became aware of what was actually contained within the documents. Once they had this awareness, they could then compare them against their own documentation as to quality, accuracy, and location. The results also support that much of the perceived learning was through participation in post-audits debriefing. Items showing large changes from baseline to post-audit indicate that CNMs showed awareness of the possibility for personal and peer improvement in documentation that might lead to decreased errors; this is consistent with learning and in changes in level of perceived competence.

Results Related to Reluctance

Considering areas that would contribute to reluctance, the only score that increased was the fear of finding errors. This reflects increased self-awareness, and may actually reflect learning rather than reluctance. Through the audit process, participants became aware of potential vulnerabilities when they previously perceived that personal documentation either met or exceeded standards. In future use of this survey, one may consider recoding this as an effect of learning rather than reluctance. In all of the pre and post audit responses, CNMs disagreed or strongly disagreed with statements that would contribute to reluctance of audit participation, suggesting reluctance. CNMs did not consider documentation audits a waste of time; average scores on this item fell between strongly disagree and disagree. This suggests that this peer audit experience was perceived as a meaningful use of time. When considering that the radiologists in Eisenberg and colleagues' work felt that their audits were a waste of time (Eisenberg et

al., 2014), it appears that CNMs perceived that the number of audits done was enough to promote learning without making the task onerous.

Results Related to Time

All participating CNMs found the audit process to be a profitable use of their time. Their responses, both in the PALT survey and in the post-audit debriefing, indicated that more than 20 minutes per survey was need to properly assess the documentation. Since no additional work time was allotted for the audit process, many CNMs indicated that four weeks was inadequate for completing the five chart audits. As seen in the findings of the PALT survey (Table 5, questions 6 and 8) and in comments shared in the debriefings, the anticipated future audit process should include adequate time for audit completion along with time for debriefings.

Limitations

This study is limited by its small sample size and self-selected sample of 15 CNMs. It may contain bias since all the participating CNMs highly supported the implementation of this QI project. The PALT survey was adapted from “Survey of Faculty Perceptions Regarding a Peer Review System” by Eisenberg et al. (2014). Our study suggests that some of the items may have yielded different result if coded within a different domain. What Eisenberg et al. considered reluctance might actually be reflective of learning (i.e., moving from unconscious to conscious incompetence). Care should be taken in writing and interpreting an adapted survey.

Conclusions

In order to design and undertake this audit process, and the study of the implementation of that process, several steps were taken. A learning framework was

developed to structure thinking about the project and the process of using the audit as a learning tool. The documentation audits tool had to be developed. The prenatal standards of the WHO, CDC, ACOG and NICE, as well as those of the NHCS were reviewed in the formulation of what constituted the components of the initial prenatal visit. In addition, a literature review was conducted. Both sources led to selection of items to be included in the audit to standardize prenatal care components for evaluation. The literature search also found Ghartey (2014), whose audit tool and scoring mechanism was adapted into the PAT audit tool.

The use of this audit tool, PAT, enabled our team to establish a baseline DQI score for which we can compare the results of our next quarterly audit, due in April 2015. The team has committed to continue this documentation audit process to assess documentation quality. The current process of doing peer audits every quarter will be maintained, repeating specific audits at least once to measure change. If warranted, a specific audit may be repeated more than once to ensure anticipated improvement.

In considering the gestalt of findings related to shared learning precepts and documentation competence, CNMs indicated that they learned from the chart audit experience about the possibility that their own documentation and that of their peers could be improved. The process significantly decreased CNM reluctance to take part in team audits, and CNMs found the time spent worthwhile – for the most part. With the exception of the increased awareness of self-vulnerability, it appeared that audit participation reduced perceived reluctance, while increasing awareness of potential vulnerability associated with inadequate care or documentation. This demonstrates that CNMs perceived that audits were worth the time and effort, can be considered a valuable

tool for learning, and should lead to improved documentation quality. The findings support the use of documentation audits to assist health care providers in developing self-awareness of their own documentation limitations, and potentially to improve EMR documentation quality and thus, serve to address the concerns raised by Parsons et al. (2012).

Based on the recommendations of the CNM team, future audits will include three instead of five EMRs to review. While the PALT survey indicated that five were not excessive, three CNMs suggested that three EMR audits would yield quality information while reducing the time commitment. During the post audit debriefing sessions, these comments were shared, and consensus was that reviewing three records will be enough to assess documentation quality, and learn documentation techniques. Survey and debriefing comments indicated support for continuing this process, with suggestions for future topics for audit focus. The CNM team strongly supports the future use of modified PAT to assess components of intrapartum care and contraceptive care. The post audit discussion by the whole team thus provided opportunity to make process modifications, fitting the needs of the CNM team.

Plan for Implementation and Dissemination of Findings

After this doctoral project, we will continue to review the audit findings during monthly CNM meetings. We will also continue to identify methods to improve documentation as a team, applying the principles of shared learning theory and error reduction (Chang & Mark, 2011).

Our immediate administrators were provided with the findings of the initial audit, and support this QI project. Once we have the results of the first two audits we plan to

share the findings at the combined physician and CNM Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology monthly meeting in May. The Audit Team Perception study results will also be shared at this time.

The results of the Audit Team Perception study will be shared at the 2015 HMO Research Network conference (Long Beach CA) with a poster presentation. It is also the topic of an in progress manuscript that will be submitted to *Nursing for Women's Health*, a publication of the Association of Women's Health, Obstetric and Neonatal Nurses. The author guidelines are found in Appendix C.

A second manuscript is planned discussing the QI process utilizing a team approach to audits. Sharing the Peer Audit Tool (PAT), it will include the results of the impact of the audit process on documentation quality. This manuscript will also include the strategies that contribute to shared learning such using team scores rather than individual scores. Ensuring that there is adequate time to review results in a non-threatening environment will be addressed in this second manuscript.

The greatest immediate impact that this project made was on members of the CNM team. The peer audit process and debriefing provided a way to evaluate documentation without fear of recourse in a productive, supportive environment. We knew there were things that we did not know, but without the ability to review records, we could not search them out. This project provided us with the vehicle to investigate our documentation, share results, and address shortcomings.

.

REFERENCES

- Alexander, G. R., & Kotelchuck, M. (2001). Assessing the role and effectiveness of prenatal care: history, challenges, and directions for future research. *Public Health Reports, 116*(4), 306-316.
- Avery, M. D., Montgomery, O., & Brandl-Salutz, E. (2012). Essential components of successful collaborative maternity care models: the ACOG-ACNM project. *Obstetrics & Gynecology Clinics of North America, 39*(3), 423-434. doi: 10.1016/j.ogc.2012.05.010
- Ayoola, A., Nettleman, M., Stommel, M., & Canady, R. (2010). Time of pregnancy recognition and prenatal care use: a population-based study in the United States. *Birth: Issues in Prenatal Care, 37*(1), 37-43. doi: 10.1111/j.1523-536X.2009.00376.x
- Baldwin, L. M., Raine, T., Jenkins, L. D., Hart, L. G., & Rosenblatt, R. (1994). Do providers adhere to ACOG standards? The case of prenatal care. *Obstetrics & Gynecology, 84*(4), 549-556.
- Banta, D. (2003). What is the efficacy/effectiveness of antenatal care and the financial and organizational implications? Copenhagen: WHO Regional Office for Europe. Retrieved from <http://www.euro.who.int/Document/E82996.pdf>
- Blencowe, H., Cousens, S., Oestergaard, M. Z., Chou, D., Moller, A. B., Narwal, R., . . . Lawn, J. E. (2012). National, regional, and worldwide estimates of preterm birth rates in the year 2010 with time trends since 1990 for selected countries: a systematic analysis and implications. *Lancet, 379*(9832), 2162-2172. doi: 10.1016/s0140-6736(12)60820-4
- Center for Disease Control. (2014). Pregnancy mortality surveillance system. Updated: March 3, 2014. *Division of Reproductive Health, National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion.*
- Chang, Y., & Mark, B. (2011). Effects of learning climate and registered nurse staffing on medication errors. *Nursing Research, 60*(1), 32-39. doi: 10.1097/NNR.0b013e3181ff73cc
- Chapman, A. (2014). *Conscious competence theory*. [Online ethical learning and development]. Retrieved from <http://www.businessballs.com/consciouscompetencelearningmodel.htm>
- Chauhan, S., Hendrix, N., Berghella, V., & Siddiqui, D. (2010). Comparisons of two national guidelines in obstetrics: American versus Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. *American Journal of Perinatology, 27*(10), 763-769. doi: 10.1055/s-0030-1253554.

- Devettere, R. (2010). *Practical decision making in health care ethics*. Washington, D.C.: Georgetown University Press.
- Dowswell, T., Carroli, G., Duley, L., Gates, S., Gulmezoglu, A. M., Khan-Neelofur, D., & Piaggio, G. G. (2010). Alternative versus standard packages of antenatal care for low-risk pregnancy. *Cochrane Database Systematic Reviews*, 10(Cd000934). doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD000934.pub2
- Eisenberg, R. L., Cunningham, M. L., Siewert, B., & Kruskal, J. B. (2014). Survey of faculty perceptions regarding a peer review system. *Journal of the American College of Radiology*, 11(4), 397-401. doi: 10.1016/j.jacr.2013.08.011
- Elder, N. C., McEwen, T. R., Flach, J., Gallimore, J., & Pallerla, H. (2010). The management of test results in primary care: does an electronic medical record make a difference? *Family Medicine*, 42(5), 327-333.
- Fein, S. P., Hilborne, L. H., Spiritus, E. M., Seymann, G. B., Keenan, C. R., Shojanian, K. G., . . . Wenger, N. S. (2007). The many faces of error disclosure: a common set of elements and a definition. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 22(6), 755-761. doi: 10.1007/s11606-007-0157-9
- Fouts, J. (2000). *Research on computers and education: Past, present and future*. Funded by Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. Retrieved from <http://www.portical.org/fouts.pdf>
- Fujino, Y., & Kawamoto, R. (2013). Effect of information and communication technology on nursing performance. *Computers Informatics Nursing*, 31(5), 244-250. doi: 10.1097/NXN.0b013e3182842103
- Ghartey, J., Lee, C., Weinberger, E., Nathan, L. M., Merkatz, I. R., & Bernstein, P. S. (2014). Using a prenatal electronic medical record to improve documentation within an inner-city healthcare network. *American Journal of Perinatology*, 31(6), 529-534. doi: 10.1055/s-0033-1354564
- Gitkind, M. J., Perla, R. J., Manno, M., & Klugman, R. A. (2014). The "physician-led chart audit: " engaging providers in fortifying a culture of safety. *Journal of Patient Safety*, 10(1), 72-79. doi: 10.1097/pts.0000000000000057
- Glantz, J. C. (2012). Obstetric variation, intervention, and outcomes: doing more but accomplishing less. *Birth*, 39(4), 286-290. doi: 10.1111/birt.12002
- Harper, M. & Helmreich, R. (2005). Identifying barriers to the success of a reporting system. In K. Henriksen, J. Battles, E. Marks, & D. Lewin (Eds.), *Advances in Patient Safety: From Research to Implementation* (pp. 167-179). Rockville, MD: Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality.

- Howson, C. P., Kinney, M. V., McDougall, L., & Lawn, J. E. (2013). Born Too Soon: Preterm birth matters. *Reproductive Health, 10*(Supplement 1), S1. doi: 10.1186/1742-4755-10-s1-s1
- Institute of Medicine. (2000). *To err is human: Building a safer health system* (L. T. Kohn, Corrigan, J., & Donaldson, M. Ed.). Washington, D.C.: National Academy Press.
- Kachalia, A., & Bates, D. W. (2014). Disclosing medical errors: The view from the USA. *Surgeon*. doi: 10.1016/j.surge.2013.12.002
- Kaiser Permanente. (2014a). *Electronic health records*. Retrieved from <http://share.kaiserpermanente.org/totalhealth/connectivity/#sthash.eJFH2qW.dpF>
- Kaiser Permanente. (2014b). *Policies: Patient safety and risk management*. Retrieved from <http://webshare.ca.kp.org/Policy/Forms/AllItems.aspx?RootFolder=%2FPolicy%2FRisk%20Management%2DPatient%20Safety&View>
- Kamath, B. D., Donovan, E. F., Christopher, R., Brodbeck, J., Slone, C., & Marcotte, M. P. (2012). Using improvement science to increase accuracy and reliability of gestational age documentation. *American Journal of Perinatology, 29*(3), 217-224. doi: 10.1055/s-0031-1285096
- Keith, N., & Frese, M. (2005). Self-regulation in error management training: emotion control and metacognition as mediators of performance effects. *Journal of Applied Psychology, 90*(4), 677-691. doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.90.4.677
- Keith, N. & Frese, M. (2008). Effectiveness of error management training: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology, 93*(1), 59-69.
- Kirkendall, E. S., Goldenhar, L. M., Simon, J. L., Wheeler, D. S., & Andrew Spooner, S. (2013). Transitioning from a computerized provider order entry and paper documentation system to an electronic health record: expectations and experiences of hospital staff. *International Journal of Medical Informatics, 82*(11), 1037-1045. doi: 10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2013.08.005
- Krans, E. E., & Davis, M. M. (2012). Preventing birthweight: 25 years, prenatal risk, and the failure to reinvent prenatal care. *American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology, 206*(5), 398-403. doi: 10.1016/j.ajog.2011.06.082
- Linthorst, G. E., Kallimanis-King, B. L., Douwes Dekker, I., Hoekstra, J. B., & de Haes, J. C. (2012). What contributes to internists' willingness to disclose medical errors? *Netherlands Journal of Medicine, 70*(5), 242-248.
- Martin, J. A., Hamilton, B. E., Ventura, S. J., Osterman, M. J., & Mathews, T. J. (2013). Births: final data for 2011. *National Vital Statistics Report, 62*(1), 1-69, 72.

- McAlearney, A. S., Sieck, C., Hefner, J., Robbins, J., & Huerta, T. R. (2013). Facilitating ambulatory electronic health record system implementation: Evidence from a qualitative study. *BioMed Research International*, 2013, 629574. doi: 10.1155/2013/629574
- McClure, E., Nathan, R., Saleem, S., Esmail, F., Garces, A., Chomba, E., . . . Goldenbert, R. (2014). First look: a cluster-randomized trial of ultrasound to improve pregnancy outcomes in low income country settings. *BioMed Central Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 14(73), 1-8. doi: 10.1186/1471-2393-14-73.
- Milchak, J., Shanahan, R., & Kerzee, J. (2012). Implementation of a peer review process to improve documentation consistency of care process indicators in the EMR in a primary care setting. *Journal of Managed Care Pharmacy*, 18(1), 46-53.
- National Institute for Health and Care Excellence. (2014). *Antenatal care: Routine care for the healthy woman*. London: NICE. Retrieved from <http://pathways.nice.org.uk/pathways/antenatal-care>
- Nicolaides, K. H. (2011). A model for a new pyramid of prenatal care based on the 11 to 13 weeks' assessment. *Prenatal Diagnosis*, 31(1), 3-6. doi: 10.1002/pd.2685
- Parsons, A., McCullough, C., Wang, J., & Shih, S. (2012). Validity of electronic health record-derived quality measurement for performance monitoring. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 19(4), 604-609. doi: 10.1136/amiajnl-2011-000557
- Robbins, C. L., Zapata, L. B., Farr, S. L., Kroelinger, C. D., Morrow, B., Ahluwalia, I., . . . Barfield, W. D. (2014). Core state preconception health indicators - pregnancy risk assessment monitoring system and behavioral risk factor surveillance system, 2009. *MMWR Surveillance Summaries*, 63(3), 1-62.
- Sammer, C. E., Lykens, K., Singh, K. P., Mains, D. A., & Lackan, N. A. (2010). What is patient safety culture? A review of the literature. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 42(2), 156-165. doi: 10.1111/j.1547-5069.2009.01330.x
- Sekerka, L. E., & Chao, J. (2003). Peer coaching as a technique to foster professional development in clinical ambulatory settings. *Journal of Continuing Education in the Health Professions*, 23(1), 30-37. doi: 10.1002/chp.1340230106
- Staton, L. J., Kraemer, S. M., Patel, S., Talente, G. M., & Estrada, C. A. (2007). Peer chart audits: a tool to meet Accreditation Council on Graduate Medical Education (ACGME) competency in practice-based learning and improvement. *Implementation Science*, 2, 24. doi: 10.1186/1748-5908-2-24
- Villar, J., Altman, D. G., Purwar, M., Noble, J. A., Knight, H. E., Ruyan, P., . . . Kennedy, S. H. (2013). The objectives, design and implementation of the INTERGROWTH-

21st Project. *BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 120 (Suppl 2), 9-26, v. doi: 10.1111/1471-0528.12047

- Vogel, J. P., Lee, A. C., & Souza, J. P. (2014). Maternal morbidity and preterm birth in 22 low- and middle-income countries: a secondary analysis of the WHO Global Survey dataset. *BioMed Central Pregnancy Childbirth*, 14, 56. doi: 10.1186/1471-2393-14-56
- Waldman, R., Kennedy, H., Kendig, S. (2012). Collaboration in maternity care: Possibilities and challenges. *Obstetrics and Gynecology Clinics of North America*, 39(3), 435-444. doi.org/10.1016/j.ogc.2012.05.011
- WHO. (2012). World health statistics 2012. World Health Organization Retrieved 2/21/2015, from WHO Department of Health Statistics and Information Systems <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs348/en/>
- Woodhouse, C., Lopez Camelo, J., & Wehby, G. L. (2014). A comparative analysis of prenatal care and fetal growth in eight South American countries. *PLoS One*, 9(3), e91292. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0091292
- Wu, A. W. (2000). Medical error: the second victim. The doctor who makes the mistake needs help too. *British Medical Journal*, 320(7237), 726-727.
- Wu, A. W., Cavanaugh, T. A., McPhee, S. J., Lo, B., & Micco, G. P. (1997). To tell the truth: ethical and practical issues in disclosing medical mistakes to patients. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 12(12), 770-775.

APPENDIX A**PERMISSION FOR USE OF “PYRAMID FOR CARE” BY K. NICOLAIDES, MD**

RE: Permission for use of "Pyramid for Care" by K. Nicolaides, MD
From FMF Education FMFEducation@fetalmedicine.comhide details
To FVPearces FVPearces@aol.com

Dear Cheryl,

Thank you for your email.

I have talked to Professor Nicolaides and he is delighted to give you a permission to use the model for your studies.

Should you have any further questions please do not hesitate to contact me.

Best regards,
Natalia Borkowska
Head of Education

The Fetal Medicine Foundation
137 Harley Street
London, W1G 6BG
United Kingdom
Tel. 0044 (0) 2070343070
Email: fmfeducation@fetalmedicine.com

APPENDIX B

PEER AUDIT LEARNING TEAM (PALT) SURVEY

PARTICIPATION IN QUALITY IMPROVEMENT: DOCUMENTATION AUDIT TEAM SURVEY

By completing this survey regarding your participation in Documentation Audits, you acknowledge that you have read the informed consent and are aware that your participation is voluntary. All responses will be coded, kept confidential and only aggregate scores for the whole Audit Team will be reported. Circle the response that best fits.

The first eight questions are about getting to know you:

1. How long have you been a health care provider in the field of Ob/Gyn?
 - a) Less than 2 years
 - b) 2 to 5 years
 - c) Over 5 years but less than 10 years
 - d) Over 10 years but less than 15 years
 - e) Over 15 years

2. I have been a member of the SCPMG Ob/Gyn team for:
 - a) Less than 2 years
 - b) 2 to 5 years
 - c) Over 5 years but less than 10 years
 - d) Over 10 years but less than 15 years
 - e) Over 15 years

3. Your age is
 - a) Under 25 years
 - b) Over 25 but less than 30 years
 - c) Over 30 years but less than 40 years
 - d) Over 40 years, but less than 50 years
 - e) Over 50 years but less than 60 years
 - f) Over 60 years

4. Your gender is
 - a) Female
 - b) Male

5. The language your parents spoke to you as a child was
 - a) English
 - b) Spanish
 - c) French
 - d) _____(write in language)

6. Your primary education, before high school was in
 a) English
 b) Spanish
 c) French
 d) _____(write in language)
7. You received your Ob/Gyn training in
 _____(write in state/country)
8. How would you rank your computer skills/education prior to your employment at KP?
 a) None, I could not even type
 b) Minimal, I knew what a mouse and email were
 c) Average, I could create and save a document, could search the internet
 d) Good, I was able to function and navigate the computer systems after orientation when starting at KP
 e) Excellent, I was able to help others with trouble shooting problems

For the next 26 items, indicate your level of agreement with the statement by circling a number.

1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Neither agree nor disagree 4=Agree 5=Strongly agree

- | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 1. My documentation is accurate. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 2. My documentation is complete. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 3. My documentation is in the appropriate place in Health Connect. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 4. Documentation Audits are a waste of time. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 5. Documentation Audits are done only to meet hospital and regulatory compliance. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 6. Documentation Audits decrease medical errors. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 7. I am afraid a significant error could be found in my care or documentation during audit of my documentation. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |

	1=Strongly Disagree	2=Disagree	3=Neither agree nor disagree	4=Agree	5=Strongly agree
8. I am afraid I could be disciplined by having my documentation audited.	1	2	3	4	5
9. I am afraid I will find a significant error in my peer's care or documentation.	1	2	3	4	5
10. I consciously select less time intensive cases to audit.	1	2	3	4	5
11. I enter an audit rating without reviewing the documentation.	1	2	3	4	5
12. I learn as I evaluate the documentation of my peers.	1	2	3	4	5
13. I learn by discussing our Documentation Audits.	1	2	3	4	5
14. I only participate in Documentation Audits because I feel forced or obliged to participate.	1	2	3	4	5
15. I will experience satisfaction by completing this documentation audit.	1	2	3	4	5
16. If I detect an error or problem in documentation as I audit, I tend to score on the side of <i>under-rating</i> the error.	1	2	3	4	5
17. Others will learn by discussing our Documentation Audits.	1	2	3	4	5
18. My ability to provide care is affected by the quality/adequacy of others' documentation.	1	2	3	4	5
19. My documentation will improve by participating in Documentation Audits.	1	2	3	4	5
20. My care will improve by participating in Documentation Audits.	1	2	3	4	5
21. My ability to provide care will improve by whole team participation in the documentation audit process	1	2	3	4	5
22. Others will experience satisfaction by completing this documentation audit.	1	2	3	4	5
23. If I detect an error or problem in the documentation, I tend to score on the side of <i>over-rating</i> the error.	1	2	3	4	5
24. Others will learn by evaluating the documentation of peers.	1	2	3	4	5
25. The documentation of my peers is accurate, complete and in the appropriate place.	1	2	3	4	5
26. The documentation of others will improve.	1	2	3	4	5

This section evaluates your perception about the requirements of your time for performing documentation audits.

Will/Did these audits take too much, too little or adequate time?

Circle the response which best describes your estimate of time or effort with each item.

1=Not enough 2=Barely adequate 3=Adequate 4=Excessive 5=Extremely excessive

- | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 1. For learning, the number of medical records I audit is | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 2. The time required to audit each medical record is | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 3. Four weeks to audit five medical records is | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 4. The effort to audit each medical record is | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 5. Each medical record audit took me approximately _____ minutes. | | | | | |

Comments: Please feel free to share any comments regarding your Documentation Audit Team participation. Do you have suggestions for improving the Audit process, or topics for future Audits? Please use the reverse side for your comments.

You have my permission to share my comments during the post audit discussion.
Circle one : yes no

Thank you for your participation!

Note. Questions adapted from "Survey of Faculty Perceptions Regarding a Peer Review System" by R. Eisenberg, M. Cunningham, B. Siewert and J. Kruskal, 2014, *Journal of the American College of Radiology*, 11(4), 397-401.

APPENDIX C

AUTHOR GUIDELINES FOR *NWH*

Guidelines for Authors

(updated December 2012)

About the Journal

Nursing for Women's Health is an official publication of the Association of Women's Health, Obstetric and Neonatal Nurses (AWHONN). Published since 1996, and currently edited by Mary C. Brucker, PhD, CNM, FACNM, it is a peer-reviewed, scholarly clinical practice journal for nurses primarily involved in the care of women and newborns. The mission is to educate, guide and report on evidence, trends and news related to women's health across the lifespan (including but not limited to the reproductive period) and obstetric and neonatal nursing. The tone is practical and reader-friendly, while upholding high standards for evidence-based, scholarly content.

Submission Criteria

Nursing for Women's Health welcomes a variety of manuscript types and topics, including but not limited to: review articles; practice innovations and trends; quality improvement projects; management of individual patients and patient populations; public health and health promotion; diseases and conditions; case studies; ethical and legal trends; legislative/regulatory news; or any other relevant, newsworthy topic suitable to the mission of the journal. The journal does not publish book reviews. We suggest that authors who wish to submit articles familiarize themselves with the journal by reading back issues and searching the online archive at nwh.awhonn.org.

Nursing for Women's Health publishes only original works. Manuscripts must not have been previously published and must not be under consideration by another publication. The journal retains all rights to works published in print and online. All authors listed on a submitted manuscript must fill out and both the copyright transfer form and the author disclosure form (both forms are attached to these guidelines and also available online as electronic PDF files). At the time when a manuscript is submitted, the corresponding author must submit copyright transfer forms and author disclosure forms for all authors listed on the manuscript.

Clinical Implications

Articles most likely to be accepted for publication in *Nursing for Women's Health* describe the most current evidence on a topic and also contain a section on the practical implications of the topic for clinicians, including but not necessarily limited to nurses. Ask yourself, does the article answer the question "So what?"

Article Categories and Length

Manuscripts can be submitted as feature articles, continuing nursing education (CNE) articles, department columns, opinion articles (commentaries), personal essays ("Reflections on Women's Health") and letters to the editor. Note: Department columns are usually invited, so please contact the editorial office at nwh@awhonn.org if you wish to submit to a column and have not been invited to do so by the journal editor or the column editor.

The following word counts are offered as guidelines:

- Feature Articles: 3,000 to 5,000 words, including references
- CNE Articles: 4,000 to 7,000 words, including references, learning objectives and post-test
- Department Columns: No more than 2,000 words, including references
- Commentaries: No more than 2,000 words, including references
- Reflections on Women's Health essays: No more than 1,500 words
- Letters to the Editor: No more than 600 words, including references

Publication Style

The writing style used in *Nursing for Women's Health* is direct, informative and conversational—the journal reads the way you would speak to your professional colleagues. When writing for *Nursing for Women's Health*, include clinical experiences and describe techniques precisely for the reader.

Cover Letter

Please include a cover letter with your submission that briefly summarizes the work; if your article was specifically solicited by the editor or a member of the editorial advisory board, please include that information in the cover letter.

Abstract

Please include a narrative abstract of no more than 125 words that summarizes the key points of your article.

Keywords

Please include three to five keywords.

Visuals & Graphics

Because visual aids enhance reader understanding, writers should include tables, lists, photographs, drawings, illustrations, etc., with their manuscript submissions whenever possible or appropriate. All visuals must be submitted along with the manuscript as separate, high-resolution (at least 300 dpi) image files, such as .JPG, .TIF, or .EPS files. We cannot accept image files in formats such as Word, Excel, or PowerPoint. *Do not embed image files within the manuscript; submit separate image files instead.* Detailed guidance on creating image files can be found at <http://authorservices.wiley.com/bauthor/illustration.asp>.

Formatting

Please keep formatting to a minimum, because if your article is accepted we will apply our standard formatting during the editing, design and typesetting process. Use a plain, 12-point Roman font, with 1" margins and double-spaced lines. If your article contains text to appear in boxes, as many NWH articles do, please **do not** actually draw a box around the text in your manuscript – we will apply this during the design and layout process. Keep the text plain, as follows:

Box 1. Risk Factors for Gestational Diabetes

Age greater than 25
Family or personal health history
Excess weight

Blinded Author Information

Because our peer review process is blinded, it is very important that there is no author identifying information anywhere in the manuscript document or in the document file name. If your article describes a project at a particular institution, please redact that information or use a blank line (_____) in place of the institution name throughout the manuscript. If your article is accepted, you will be able to add that information back in before the article is prepared for publication. It is fine to have author identifying information in the cover letter.

Line Numbering

Manuscripts must contain continuous line numbering. To accomplish this in Microsoft Word (2010 version), click "Page Layout" and then "Line Numbering" and choose "Continuous."

Permissions

Sources of quotations and all other borrowed materials must be clearly identified. Long quotations, figures, tables or photographs from previously published sources must be accompanied by the written permission of the copyright holder. This includes any table or figure that replicates 50 percent or more of another table or figure. It is the responsibility of the author to secure written permission from copyright holders to reproduce copyrighted materials with their article. If the copyright holder charges a fee to grant permission, the fee is the responsibility of the author seeking permission. Written permissions must be submitted online along with the manuscript. All visuals, photos and graphics submitted without such permissions will be rejected. Writers must also provide accurate credit information as to the source; this includes names and copyrights where applicable. If submitting photographs of people, the author must submit signed release forms indicating that the people depicted in the photo have given their permission for their likeness to be used in the article.

References

Cite primary references only. Seek out and use the most current and up-to-date references (evidence) in your text; lack of current referencing is one of the most common reasons articles are rejected for publication. By most current and up-to-date, we mean references published within the past five years, unless there are classical or critical older references that are vital to your article.

Matters of fact that are well-established in nursing, such as normal pulse rate ranges, don't need to be referenced. In formatting your cited references, follow the standards set for references only in the *Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association*, Sixth Edition (APA) but also add in the volume number and DOI for the publication when available. Use generic names of all drugs and devices; put brand name equivalents (when applicable) in parentheses upon first mention in the text. To read more about APA style and referencing, visit www.apa.org.

Peer Review

All submitted articles are reviewed by up to three peer reviewers considered familiar with the specific subject matter. When necessary, articles may receive additional review to ensure accuracy and usefulness. Our process is double blinded, so that reviewers do not know the identity of authors and vice versa.

Online Open

OnlineOpen is available to authors of primary research who wish to make their articles available to non-subscribers on publication or whose funding agencies require grantees to archive the final version. With OnlineOpen, the author, the author's funding agency, or the author's institution pays a fee to ensure that the article is made available to non-subscribers upon publication via Wiley Online Library and deposited in the funding agency's preferred archive. For the full list of terms and conditions, see http://wileyonlinelibrary.com/onlineopen#OnlineOpen_Terms.

Any authors wishing to publish their articles OnlineOpen will be required to complete the payment form available from our website at: https://authorservices.wiley.com/bauthor/onlineopen_order.asp.

Prior to acceptance, authors are not required to inform the Editorial Office that they intend to publish OnlineOpen if they do not wish to. All OnlineOpen articles are treated in the same way as any other articles. They go through the journal's standard peer-review process and will be accepted or rejected based on their own merit.

Submitting Your Manuscript at Editorial Manager

All submissions to *Nursing for Women's Health* must be made online at Editorial Manager at www.editorialmanager.com/nwh. DO NOT mail a hard copy of your manuscript to the editorial office. The corresponding author must register at Editorial Manager and enter complete contact information, including a current email address, phone number and mailing address. Because all correspondence about the submission is completed via email, please be sure to add "@editorialmanager.com" to your email program's list of Safe Senders, otherwise important emails regarding your submission could be filtered as junk or spam. Authors needing assistance with Editorial Manager should refer to the Editorial Manager tutorial at www.editorialmanager.com/homepage/DOCS/Author_Tutorial.pdf.

Required Forms

All authors listed on the manuscript must fill out and sign the copyright transfer form and the author disclosure form, save them as a digital file (such as PDF) and supply them to the corresponding author so that she or he can submit them online at Editorial Manager at the time the manuscript is submitted. The copyright transfer form can be found online at www.blackwellpublishing.com/pdf/NWH_CTF.pdf and the author disclosure form can be found online at www.editorialmanager.com/nwh/account/Author%20Disclosure%20Form.pdf.

PLEASE USE THE MANUSCRIPT CHECKLIST ON THE NEXT PAGE AS A GUIDE WHEN MAKING YOUR SUBMISSION...

MANUSCRIPT CHECKLIST

Your submission to the journal via Editorial Manager (www.editorialmanager.com/nwh) should include the following:

- a cover letter (if applicable, please tell us if your paper was invited and, if so, who invited it)
- a narrative abstract no longer than 125 words, which summarizes the key points of your article
- three to five keywords
- absolutely no identifying author information on any pages of the manuscript or in the document file name
- clearly organized sections with subheadings
- a section on the practical implications for clinicians
- all lines double-spaced and numbered continuously
- lists, charts, tables, illustrations or figures that enhance the reader's understanding of the topic
- artwork, photographs or illustrations submitted as separate, high-resolution files (at least 300 dpi) in .TIF, .JPG or .EPS format (formats such as Word, Excel and PowerPoint will not be accepted). Note: Tables and boxes do not need to be submitted as image files; they can be submitted as part of the manuscript Word document.
- a list of links to online resources for additional information, as appropriate
- references cited to the style set forth in the APA Sixth Edition
- written permission to reproduce any previously copyrighted material
- signed copyright transfer forms for all authors listed on the manuscript
- signed author disclosure forms for all authors listed on the manuscript

Questions? Contact the editorial office at nwh@awhonn.org or call toll-free at 1-866-794-2337.

APPENDIX D

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 1

Peer Audits of Electronic Medical Records: Strategy for Quality Improvement: Audits

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
Developed and implemented chart audits Physician Led Audits (PLA) improve use of standards, comparison for national benchmarking, provide for continuous QI (Gitkind, Perla, Manno, & Klugman, 2014).	QI Descriptive implementation for chart audit procedure Developed 3 audit tools specific to Setting: Outpt ambulatory Inpatient Procedural Each audit tool 1 page, yes/no	UMass 3 campus inpt and outpt settings 256 physicians 1909 PLAs over 10 months	Which areas had highest rates of return Based on volumes of returns specific to departments	Highest yields in depts. Surgery, Medicine, Peds Providers learned to recognize substandard documentation, improvement strategies were discussed and implemented Need for dept. leaders to support efforts Blocks: system to collect, collate, generate reports unfunded mandate, time &, timely reports	Study to evaluate methodology for involving staff, did not include outcome data of audits However noted improved documentation without deficiencies in a subsequent regulatory survey Stressed importance of engineering daily quality standards to ensure awareness and compliance Has audit tools included
Evaluate adequacy of documentation of prenatal records within EMR vs paper charts (Ghartey et al.,	Descriptive Pre & Post Implementation IV: type of record: paper or EMR DV: adequacy of	Two sites Bronx inner city care clinic; OB approx. 500 births/yr. 300 charts:	Charts reviewed, data elements scored -1 absent; 0 if element not indicated; 1 incomplete; 2 complete documentation Raw score Max 30	Adequacy of documentation varied on type of practice Non-teaching site had lower scores PQI ratios:	EMR followed same format as paper chart Higher risk clients in one clinic Practice affected by

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
2014)	documentation Three arms: Study: Prenatal EMRs 2003 (teaching) Two Control Historical: 2002 paper (teaching) Contemp: 2003 paper in adjoining clinic (non-teaching)	101paper, 100 EMR, 89 contemp Two sites: Comprehensive Family Care: teaching facility Comprehensive Health Care: not a teaching facility, but faculty	divided by indicated elements Elements evaluated: Medical Hx, substance use scr, family Hx inheritable disorders, psychosocial scr, initial PE, FH & FHR at all visits after 1 st tri, HIV counseling & testing, triple scr testing or ref for amnio, level II utz, gest diab scr	EMR 1.71 (-1 to 2.12) Paper 1.75 (-0.25 to 2) Non teach 1.54 (-0.82 to 2) $p \leq .001$ teaching vs non-teaching EMR vs paper no statistical signif difference	teaching vs non- teaching site Did not find significant improvement in EMR over paper <i>Would provide good components for audit tool</i>
Opinions of radiologists toward participation in peer review process & perceived value of participation (Eisenberg, Cunningham, Siewert, & Druskal, 2013).	Cross-sectional self-report Descriptive Radiology faculty views about peer review system for 6 years. IV: Peer chart audits DV: Perception in value of chart audits on quality improvement indicators Each radiologist audits 2.5% of all cases, to max 300 cases/year. Group has peer audited > 60,000 cases/6 years	Conv sample Dept of Rad, Harvard Med School Large urban medical center 50/52 (96.2%) radiologists self-selected anonymous Q'naire Data collected in 2013	Tool: Survey Monkey Questions generated by authors: Demographics Rated statements Likert scale 1-5 1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree; or 1 never to 5 almost always Multiple choice Free text answers Q'naire Assess multiple aspects on peer review: methods for case selection & scoring, rating & presentation of errors, error mgmt. & effect of peer review on individual performance.	< 60% answered demographic Almost half agree peer review improves performance & is valuable, one third indicated it decreases medical errors Most do not review own data 1.85 (1 = never; 2 = rarely) 44% agreed peer review waste of time, 58% agreed peer review done only for hosp/regulatory requirements 46% felt forced	Single institution Self-designed Q'naire; No validity/reliability tests Unknown number of questions asked. Wide variety in types of questions asked, did not indicate how non- Likert questions were quantified Peer review should not focus on error identification & measurement, but on Quality Improvement. <i>Number of audits should not be onerous</i>

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
Inpt health care providers perceptions able to safely care for pts while changing from one CPOE with paper medical record DOC to EMR. (Kirkendall, Goldenhar, Simon, Wheeler, & Spooner, 2013).	Descriptive Pre & Post Implementation Self-report IV: New hospital EMR system implementation DV: Providers perceptions of problems associated with EMR T1: Surveyed prior to implementation & T2 One year after implementation of new EMR system	Single institution CCHMC in OH 523 bed tertiary care academic pediatric facility 7213 inpt staff eligible response rate T1 377 (5.2%) T2 983 (13.65%) Data collected 1/2010 (T1) &1/2011(T2)	IV: Electronic order system and paper pt. care DOC replaced by new Epic systems total EMR DV: Tool: Survey Monkey using modified Information Systems Expectations and Experiences (I-SEE) 35 ques with 1-7 Likert scale: privacy and security, workflow changes, pt care distractors, unintended consequences	All trends from T1 to T2 increased SS in: p < .001 Job Satis p < .001 Pt. care qual & safety p =.003 Support of organization p < .001 Pt care "rights"	Single pediatric institution Low response rates Providers concerns about unintended consequences with EMR technology. Need to provide ongoing assessment of EMR documentation quality, identify potential unintended consequences
Assess impact QPI project improving accuracy /reliability in gestational documentation within hospital EMR on Ohio birth certificates (Kamath et al., 2012)	Prospective cohort study Response to critical events, only 25% GA reliability prior to QPI IV: QPI strategies DV: accurate GA in clinical management,, research data bases, and Ohio birth certificates	Convenience sample: single hospital 7000 births/year, 8795 births in 2009 One hospital in Cinn. With > 100 obstet providers in outpt settings	IV: 4 phases -1., training RNs how to enter data in EMR, standardized workflow, 2. Standardized H&P completed by all outpt offices, 3. Supervisor Audit for complete H&P, , developed pregnancy card for each pt. with edd, utz and lab information 4. Office practices were audited, feedback and continued learning sessions	Completion went from 25% pre intervention to 78% post intervention Increased communication of high risk status between office and hospital	Response to two events: 2 iatrogenic premature births, and 2009 bill passage requiring hospitals to publicly report performance measures; dependent on GA Prevented 2 additional iatrogenic premature births during study
Assess validity of quality measures in EMR in computer	Descriptive Retrospective Comparison of reports	Convenience sample 57 primary care practices in NY	IV: Quality reporting tool adopted by New York City Primary Care Information Project: automated quality	Manual review showed DOC often missed in automated reports due to lack of ability of software	Limitations: EMR evaluated used eClinicalWorks & may not be generalizable to

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
generated audit reports. Identify variations in DOC on software to process data entered. (Parsons, McCullough, Wang & Shih, 2012).	generated by computer review to manual review of 11 clinical quality measures in EMR. IV: Type of EMR review, computer vs manual review DV: Presence of 11 quality measures in EMR	City 120 EMR /4081 EMR R selected for manual review	reporting tool Displays whether practice has met recommended preventative services for each pt. DV: Trained reviewers checked for presence in: DOC: Age, gender, vitals, dx, meds, lab results, dx images, vaccinations, counseling, referrals from the most recent visit. Searched problem list, medical HX, social HX, progress notes (CC, HPI, assessment), procedures, DX images & lab tests Compared findings with those found with EMR derived software	to recognize data Automated reports correlation to manual reports ranged from 10.7 to 99.9%. Vitals, vaccinations & meds had highest DOC congruence in 91.6 to 99.8% Diagnoses with free text entries were not recognized. Unrecognizable DOC seen in 6 quality measures:	other systems. <i>Suggests: more studies to assess validity of EMR derived quality measures, & to understand the limitations of EMR generated data.</i> <i>Regular prompts, training & feedback to promote accurate DOC that will translate into the EMR.</i> <i>Chart audits to accurately assess quality indicators not only for performance but for accurate DOC and recognition of DOC</i>
Develop & implement peer review process, & report resulting changes in DOC; & Standardize peer review process; minimize variations in DOC standards (Milchak, Shanahan, &	Pre & post test Descriptive IV: Peer review development & implementation in pharmacy setting Included perceptions of pharmacists about peer review process DV1: DOC quality in	KPCO NFP group model health maintenance organization; 19 primary care clinics 33 clinical pharmacy specialists Collaboratively work with physicians to develop drug	IV: 5 member team to create standardized audit tool, develop peer review process, gain support from pharmacy team: Initial resistance due to perception motivation was disciplinary Audit tool One page 22 item based on protocol (yes/no) No = failure to comply with requirement	Peer review has not been used for disciplinary actions, pharmacy Non-compliance of any aspect of protocols in DOC decreased from 14.1% to 2.5% ($p = .001$)	Frequent revisions of audit tool creates difficulty to compare results over time No assessment of inter-rater reliability Flexibility of audit tool enables use in other groups Rotate membership of peer review team every 2-3 years with

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
Kerzee, 2012).	EMR in pharmacists interventions	Mgmt therapy protocols 1856 peer reviews between 2007 & 2010	Reviewer could comment on each item DV: Incidence of non-compliance in any aspect of protocols in DOC		understanding that performing peer review encourages learning and professional development
Evaluate office process office Mgmt of test results. Assess whether EMR increase DOC of rad and lab test results. Assess abnormal results documented, if, pt. informed of follow up plan. (Elder, McEwen, Flach, Gallimore & Palleria, 2010).	Mixed Methods Descriptive Exploratory interviews Observational Retrospective chart reviews of both paper chart & EMR IV: Type of medical record, paper chart vs EMR DV1: Test results correctly Documented DV2: How & when pt. notified of results documented DV3: How & when pt. notified of abnormal results; & plan for follow up documented.	Purposeful convenience sample Data collected 2007-2009 Site visits of 8 independent family medicine offices in OH 1-4 days by FP MD & human factors grad. student 4 offices paper 4 offices EMR DOC 25 randomly selected charts with ordered lab or rad tests from each office Total tests: 461 Paper = 187 EMR = 274	Observed, questioned staff & assessed specific standardized office protocols/adherence for test tracking, clinician signature, interpretation, pt notification, & abnormal results follow up methods. Audit of both: Paper charts & EMR DV 1: - Results in the right place, -. Clinician signature on result, -. Clinician interpretation in the chart, -. Presence of pt. notification of results DV2: Method/Timing of pt. notification of results documented. DV3: clinically abnormal test results, additional assessment of DOC for pt. notification and type of follow up documented	No consistent manner for handling normal or abnormal test results in any office; varied on type of test & place performed Paper & EMR DOC % yes / % yes Appropriate place 98 / 100 Clinician signature 86 / 100 Clinician interpretation 64 / 73 Pt notification 66 / 80 Successful pt. notification of abnormal results and type of follow up DOC ranged 20-90% Individual office DOC of abnormal results follow up Paper (4 offices) 20%. 28%, 41%, & 64% EMR (4 offices) 55%, 58%, 67%, & 90%	Limited generalizability Independent office sites in OH in combination of rural, suburban & urban settings Small sample with minimal office descriptions of DPW & population served; no statistical analysis of offices' demographics, Wide variation in payer mix EMR had improved DOC, but lack of standardized processes for results both normal & abnormal create potential vulnerability

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
			Yes/No as to whether documentation was present		
Peer chart audits by effects on foot care DOC in DM patients in the absence of formal feed back (Staton, Kraemer, Patel, Talente & Estrada, 2007).	<p>Descriptive EMR review</p> <p>Time-Series design</p> <p>Reviewed DOC of foot care before & after performance of chart audits of peers' DOC</p> <p>IV: Performance of chart audits peers' DOC on foot care DM pts</p> <p>DV: DOC of foot exams by DQIP guidelines:</p> <p>DV: DOC of Hx or ROS related to feet; prevalence of foot abnormalities, & interventions</p>	<p>Convenience sample</p> <p>347 pts with DM in TN university-based clinic by internal medicine residents.</p> <p>Three separate audits</p> <p>June 2003, Sept 2003 & May 2004</p> <p>Each internal medicine residents audited 2-5 peers' charts during each of the three audit phases.</p> <p>Simultaneous audit of the auditors' charts by their peers</p>	<p>IV: Audit tool developed by researchers</p> <p>Dichotomous</p> <p>Yes/No for each criteria</p> <p>Tool based on DQIP guidelines:</p> <p>DOC of Hx or ROS related to feet</p> <p>4 criteria</p> <p>DOC of abnormalities of foot</p> <p>4 criteria</p> <p>DOC of interventions for foot abnormalities</p> <p>4 criteria</p> <p>DV: Same criteria evaluated in peers charts for the auditors' charts</p>	<p>Peer chart audits improved DOC of all three DQIP measures:</p> <p>-neuro ($p = .001$)</p> <p>-vasc ($p < .001$)</p> <p>-skin ($p < .005$)</p> <p>DOC of all three increased from 6% to 24% ($p < .001$)</p> <p>No difference in DOC of Hx or ROS related to feet. ($p > .05$)</p> <p>No difference in DOC of foot abnormalities. ($p > .11$).</p> <p>No difference in DOC of interventions. ($p > .10$)</p>	<p>Limitations: Authors acknowledge that improvement in DOC does not necessarily indicate improved care, as there was no difference in the documented prevalence of foot abnormalities overall during the audits</p> <p><i>Improvements occurred without formal instructional feedback</i></p> <p><i>Authors credit the audit with more impact for learning than any discussion of foot care based on prior experience</i></p>
Assess variation in DOC accuracy between CNMs & MDs in birth certificate & hospital discharge data	<p>Retrospective chart reviews compared</p> <p>CNM and MD DOC accuracy in: maternal medical conditions, pregnancy complications; &</p>	<p>2699 women delivered in 10 WA hosps in 2000.</p> <p>Hosps included have both MD</p>	<p>Three categories of data sources</p> <p>-Hosp disch data</p> <p>-Birth certificate data</p> <p>-Combination of hosp disch and birth certificate data</p> <p>used to calculate TPR if</p>	<p>CNMs had consistently higher TPR DOC rates; not SS except in Pre-eclampsia ($p < .001$)</p> <p>Overall DOC quality better for CNMs</p>	<p>Underpowered for variables evaluated</p> <p>Small sample size of 220 women</p> <p>CI imprecise due to sample delivered by</p>

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
(Bradford, Cardenas, Camacho-Carr, Lydon-Rochelle, 2007).	presence of intrapartum & postpartum events. IV: Type of OB provider: CNM or MD. DV: True positive rate for complications calculated using birth certificate data & hosp data for each type of provider	and CNM attended births. 2479 (91.8%) by MDs 220 (8.2%) by CNMs	health complications existed during pregnancy	: Uniformly more detail oriented with greater accuracy of documentation, but SS not achieved	CNM not adequate enough to evaluate uncommon conditions, and affects generalizability Larger midwifery services with greater volumes need to document outcomes, doing chart audits add to the data base utilized to evaluate CNM care
Evaluate communication between outpt, labor unit & u/s unit through use of PNRs intrapartum pre & post implementation EPNR. Historically complete absence of PNR on all women under 32 weeks GA (Bernstein, Farinelli & Merkatz, 2005)	Retrospective Time-Series design Reviewed intrapartum inpt. charts before & after implementation of EPNR for presence of PNR. IV: Implementation of EPNR DV: DOC in intrapartum inpt records: 1. Presence of PNR 2. Median number of days from last outpt. visit entry in PNR to admission 3. DOC of prenatal utz	Convenience sample Single inner city family care clinic in Bronx, NY. N = 43 charts pre EPNR Aug 2002 n = 43 charts post EPNR Aug 2003 4000 deliveries per year in affiliated teaching hosp. Mostly uninsured or Medicaid, 45% Hisp, 30% AA, 25% Non Hisp. (Caucasian	IV: If present, type of PNR: paper or EPNR DV: Intrapartum inpt. records for: Presence of prenatal record: whether there was a PNR on the intrapartum inpt record Yes/No If PNR was present, then audited: Last Documented prenatal visit in PNR: Median number of days from last outpt. visit to day of 7Intrapartum Inpt Adm.	No SS difference in groups in demographics or clinical characteristics PNR missing in inpt charts: Pre EPR 7 (16%) ^a Post EPR 1 (2%) ^a (<i>p</i> < .05) Number of days Pre EPR 36 days (1 to 102) ^f Post EPR 4 days (0-30) ^f (<i>p</i> < .001) PNC u/s DOC missing in inpt record	Limitations: Documents were from single site of multisite system Paper based records under 32 weeks gest age were unavailable; now available from initial visit throughout prenatal course Historical comment: During month of EPR implementation: computer system continued to function during great blackout of the Northeast in August 2003 due to emergency generators

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
		or Asian)	Presence of u/s DOC: Either actual report or report summary Cross checked with review of u/s unit records to verify u/s had been performed during PNC Yes/No	Pre EPR 7 (16%) ^a Post EPR 0 missing (<i>p</i> = .01)	

Notes. Adm =admission; AA = African American; Amnio = amniocentesis, CC = chief complaint; CCHMC = Cincinnati Children’s Hospital Medical Center; CNM = certified nurse-midwife; Comm = communication; Contemp =contemporaneous, Conv = convenience, CPOE = computerized order entry system; C/S = cesarean section; Del = delivery; Dept = department; DFM = Department of Family Medicine; Diab = diabetes, DM: Diabetes Mellitus; Disch = discharge; Diff = different; DOC = Documentation; DPW= daily patient workload; DQIP = diabetes quality improvement project; DV = dependent variable; DX = diagnosis; edd = estimated date of delivery; EMR = electronic medical record; EPNR = electronic prenatal record; FH = fundal height, FHR = fetal heart rate, FP = Family Practice; GA = gestational age; Gest. = gestation; Grad = graduate; H & P = history and physical, Hisp. = Hispanic; HIV = human immunodeficiency virus, Hosp = hospital; Hosps = hospitals; HPI = history of present illness; HTN = hypertension; Hx = history; IV = independent variable; Inpt. = inpatient; KPCO = Kaiser Permanente Colorado; Lab = Laboratory; Max = maximum; Mgmt = management; MD = medical Doctor; Meds. = medications; Med-surg. unit = Medical surgical unit; NFP = not for profit; NFF=non federally funded; NR = nonrandom; Nur = Nurse; Nurs. = Nurses; Nursg. = Nursing; NY = New York; OB = obstetric; OH – Ohio; Outpt. = outpatient; PE = physical examination, Peds = Pediatrics; PLA = Physician Led Chart Audits; Pt. = Patient; PNC = prenatal care; PNR = prenatal records; QI = Quality Improvement; Ques = questions; Q’naire = questionnaire; R = random; Rad = radiology; Ref = referral, ROS = Review of Systems; Satis = satisfaction; scr = screen; SS = statistically significant; T = time; Tm = team; TN = Tennessee; TPR = true positive rate; Tri = trimester, UMass = University of Massachusetts; US = United States; Utz = ultrasound, Var. = variable; WA = Washington state.

^aValues are n (%); ^r Values are median (range).

Table 2

Peer Audits of Electronic Medical Records: Strategy for Strategy for Quality Improvement: Shared Learning

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
Learning climate influence moderates relationship of error producing conditions and incidence of severe errors (Chang & Mark, 2011).	Secondary analysis Cross sectional descriptive IV: Key Moderating variable: Learning Climate DV: Occurrence of severe meds error incident reports	Multi centered, 146 R US NFP & NFF hosps., 286 med-surg. Units 4954 nurses Data collected in 2003-2004 at 3 time points over 6 month period (T1, T2, & T3)	Key IV: Nurs. Q'naire. 3 separate Q'naires. over 6 mos. (T1, T2 & T3) Specific to learning climate: Error Orientation Scale 13 item five point Likert scale -Willingness to reveal errors -Degree of open communication about errors -Extent that nurses consider errors and diagnose sources DV: Errors as per severe incident reports	Learning climate moderates effects of number of RNs in nurse mix with meds errors. ($p < .01$) Significant relationship of learning climate to errors ($p < .01$) As learning climate improved, severe meds errors decreased	Only NFP and NFF No descriptors of hosps. Low sensitivity of incident reports compared to chart review or direct observation Informational sharing decreases potential for errors. "Learning from errors is the process of creating, retaining, and transferring effective knowledge and practices to reduce the likelihood of similar errors occurring in the future" (Chang & Mark, 2011, p. 37)
Explore qualities of peer coaching: 1. Perceived benefits of coaches from PC 2. Contribution	Mixed methods Qualitative Grounded theory & thematic analysis Descriptive quantitative IV: Role of coaching peers	Conv sample, 13 interviews of Dept of FM MDs in OH All had prior training in PC in faculty development workshops to become preceptors.	Individual tape recorded guided critical incident interviews of 50-70 minutes. 3 questions: "What are you getting out of being a coach? To what extent has this coaching experience affected your role as a physician preceptor?	Two separate clustering of themes identified: 1. Reflection & teaching a. use of reflection skills b. sees bigger picture c. focus on learner d. enhances well-being e. motivation to teach	Limitations: self-selection with small sample size. Two interviews not used to eliminate potential long term memory bias of encounters over 2 years prior to interview: total of 11 interviews used.

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
of professional development of coach through PC (Sekerka & Chao, 2005).	DV: Perceived benefit to coached persons & persons who coached	Reflected specific coaching encounter within last 2 years	What happens to you as a result of your coaching experience?" (Sekerka & Chao, 2005, p 31). Transcripts reviewed & Codebook developed by researcher. Transcripts coded by both researcher & assistant, inter-rater reliability of .91. Q'naire completed by both coach & person coached. 24 questions Likert 1-5 point scale, 5 = excellent. Reflect coach's contribution, effectiveness; & satisfaction with coaching interaction.	2. Personal learning & change a. notes own contribution b. learns something new c. experiences change d. positive self-assessment Q'naire results: Coaches rated themselves lower than person coached: Mean scores: Person Coached: 4.2 Coaches: 3.8. Both coach & person coached indicated positive experience.	Published in 2005, no comment when data was collected <i>Collegial interaction rather than supervisory interaction benefits both the coach & person coached. Encourages cross learning & support</i> <i>Ongoing learning & professional development by both the coach & the person coached through PC</i> <i>Associated with personal change & growth</i>

Notes: Comm = communication; Conv = convenience; DV = dependent variable; FM = Family Medicine; FP = Family Practice; = hospitals; IV = independent variable; MD = medical Doctor; Meds. = medications; Med-surg. unit = Medical surgical unit; NFP = not for profit; NFF=non federally funded; Nur = Nurse; Nurs. = Nurses; OH – Ohio; PC = peer coaching; Q'naire = questionnaire.

Table 3

Peer Audits of Electronic Medical Records: Strategy for Strategy for Quality Improvement: Participation and Error Discovery

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
Identify factors influence willingness to disclose errors (Linthorst, Kallimanis-King, Dekker, Hoekstra, & deHaes, 2012).	Descriptive self report Mixed methods Surveys Interviews	Netherlands, five teaching hospitals <i>11 internists/interns</i> <i>51% participation</i> <i>4 months</i>	3 domains: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Near miss Minor error Major error Age, gender, position in dept, error Hx, error reporting Hx 5 pt. Likert scale items motivation, behavioral control, departmental culture Intention and who to report based on severity of error <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Colleagues, head of dept., risk committee, patients 	Motives to report error protect patients, so that others can learn from it, in the interest of the clinician for less guild, Motives not to report: negative publicity Direct correlation with dept. culture to willingness to report $\alpha = .95$	Limited response rate Attitudes toward disclosure positive, Prevention of future errors Educational value It is one's responsibility to Disclose Negatives of disclosure: Negative publicity Reputation harm Unfavorable response from patient
Identify barriers to participation in reporting system Cite under reporting of errors by as much as 96% (Harper & Helmreich, 2005).	Descriptive Mixed methods surveys Self-report surveys Structure interviews	Two hospitals affiliated with University of Texas 41% response rate 858 nurses and physicians	5 pt. Likert scale Specific questions to mandatory reporting system Use and perceived effectiveness Reasons for not using Overcoming barriers	Strong opinions for responsibilities to address errors Supported by nonpunitive, trusted source of reporter Structured data collection with immediate feedback Customized reporting programs based on profession	Critical components include: Nonpunitive, customized process with focus on distribution and feedback Focus on systemic factors FAA grants pilots immunity from punishment in return for voluntary submission of reports = 30,000 reports per year

Notes. FAA = Federal Aviation Administration.

Table 4

Peer Audits of Electronic Medical Records: Strategy for Quality Improvement: Prenatal Care Guidelines and Evidence

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
Describes study protocol for RCT evaluating OB utz use in low-resource settings Including training for UTZ use Sponsored by Gates Foundation (McClure et al., 2014).	Descriptive IV 1: use of OB utz; IV 2: training of sonographers DV: Morbidity and mortality rates in clusters 58 clusters: 29 intervention weeks and 32-36 weeks 29 control	Five Low-income countries 500 births in specific "catchment" areas Guatemala, Zambia, Democratic Republic of Congo, Kenya, and Pakistan Women ≥ 16 weeks Plan to identify key demographic data, baseline differences	Pregnancy outcomes from both arms by the MNH registry personnel	Initial findings have supported the Gates Foundation to continue to place ultrasounds in countries at risk	Community sensitization for use of utz Need for referral institution for staff trained to review utz findings, and manage complications "Decreasing cost and increasing availability of utz in low-resource settings, understanding the impact not only on the health of the mother and fetus, but on the health setting..." (McClure, et al., 2014, p. 6)
Collaborative model presented by ACOG and ACNM (Waldman, Kennedy, & Kendig, 2011)	Descriptive/comparative outline for collaborative practice presented at National ACOG and ACNM meetings in 2011	Review	N/A	Reviews benefits and challenges of collaboration in Interprofessional obstetrical health care settings	Reviews barriers to collaborative care, and provides practical suggestions Reviews the joint statements on collaborative practice presented by ACNM and ACOG
Examine the relationship of pregnancy recognition	Secondary analysis IV: Pregnancy recognition DV: Use of PNC:	PRAMS multistate data (29 states) surveys of women with live-born	Time of pregnancy recognition Demographics: ethnicity, age, gravidity, married, education, insurance status, SES	92.5% recognize pregnancy by 12 weeks 79.9% initiate PNC ≤ 12 weeks,	Pregnancy recognition is strong predictor of PNC Limitations: self-report, recall bias

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
with beginning PNC (Ayoola, Nettleman, Stommel, & Canady, 2010)	Timing and number of visits	infants (mail & telephone) between 2000 and 2004 136,373 women (missing data excluded from study)	Time of pregnancy recognition Participation in PNC (yes/no) # Visits Time of PNC initiation	0.4% : No PNC 35.8%: < 11 PNC visits 54% : 11 to 15 PNC visits 9.7% ≥ 15 PNC visits Early pregnancy identification -increased odds of early PNC (OR = 6.05) -number of visits (OR = 0.71)	<i>No comparison with outcomes; makes the assumption that number of visits implies adequate care</i>
Compare ACOG and RCOG published guidelines between 5/99 and 12/07 (Chauhan, Hendrix, Berghella, & Siddiqui, 2010).	Review, Compared all published PB (ACOG) & GG (RCOG) for Agreement, numbers and types, reference sources, and if topical references were same	Convenience, literature review Two authors reviewed each publication	Documented /compared for each current guideline: # of authors; Total # and type of recommendations with # of citations; publishing location; and if guidelines: agree, disagree or not comparable	99-07 published ACOG 42 PBs RCOG 27 GGs ACOG:RCOG Avg # of authors (1-5) 1 : 2 Avg # of recom (0-25) per guideline 7 : 15 Level of evidence A, B, & C were similar Ref #: 68:53	ACOG considers meta-analysis as separate findings, while RCOG considers meta-analysis as 1A: highest level of evidence, RCT =Level I in both, Controlled= level II RCOG has “good practice points” Evid: D& E level in ACOG, not in RCOG Only 22% correlation on same topics for citations; Recom of the common obstetric guidelines not comparable the majority of the time.>50% in 9 topics disagreed <i>“National guidelines are a rigorous analysis of the publications and formulation of evidence-based recommendation...optimize</i>

Purpose (Source)	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, author conclusions / Notes
					<i>outcomes, minimize costs, and mitigate litigation.”</i> (Chauhan et al., 2010, p. 766)
Evaluate Adherence to ACOG PNC standards (Baldwin et al., 1994)	Descriptive, random chart audits IV : type of provider DV: adherence to PNC standards per ACOG	PNC records in Wash. 9/1/88 to 8/30/89 5 types providers Urban Ob/Gyn Rural Ob/Gyn Urban FP MDs Rural FP MDs Urban CNMs	Abstraction of PNC records compared with ACOG guidelines	CNMs records most closely matched ACOG Overall, less adherence ≥ 30wks fundal height, fetal activity ≥ fetal presentation	Providers in various settings adhere to clinical guidelines if disseminated and implemented

Notes. ACOG = American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists; Avg = average; CNM =certified nurse midwife; Evid = evidence; GA = gestational age; GG = Green Guidelines; MNH = Global Network’s Maternal Newborn Health; OB = obstetrics; PB = Practice Bulletins; PNC = Prenatal Care; RCOG = Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists; recom = recommendations; PRAMS = Pregnancy Risk Assessment and Monitoring Systems; Ref = References; utz = ultrasound; SES = socioeconomic status; Wash = Washington state; *OR* = Odds ratio.

